

C O R T E X ²

D4.1 – Legal and Ethical Inventory

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101070192. This document reflects only the author's view, and the EU Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

D4.1 – Legal and Ethical Inventory

Project Title	COoperative Real-Time EXperiences with EXTended reality
Project Acronym	CORTEX ²
Grant Agreement No	101070192
Instrument	HORIZON Innovation Actions
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-25
Start Date of Project	September 1, 2022
Duration of Project	36 months

Name of the Deliverable	Ethical and legal inventory
Number of the Deliverable	D4.1
Related WP Number and Name	WP4
Related Task Number and Name	T4.1 - Ethical and legal inventory
Deliverable Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Due Date	31.08.2023
Deliverable Submission Date	31.08.2023
Task Leader/Main Author(s)	CiTIP - KU LEVEN Prof Anton Vedder

	Dr Maja Nisevic Franklyn Ohai
Contributing Partners	Azucena Garcia Palacios (UJI) Alain Pagani (DFKI)
Reviewer(s)	Helbert Emmanuel (ALE) Alain Pagani (DFKI)

Keywords

GDPR, data governance, natural language processing, extended reality, mix reality, virtual reality, augmented reality, artificial intelligence, generative AI, virtual assistants, teleconferencing, remote work.

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	30/05/2023		KUL
v0.2	12/06/2023		KUL
V0.3	07/07/2023		KUL
V0.4	25/07/2023		KUL
V1.0	18/08/2023	Coordinator review	Alain Pagani

Disclaimer

This document is provided with no warranties whatsoever, including any warranty of merchantability, non-infringement, fitness for any particular purpose, or any other warranty with respect to any information, result, proposal, specification or sample contained or referred to herein. Any liability, including liability for infringement of any proprietary rights, regarding the use of this document or any information contained herein is disclaimed. No license, express or implied, by estoppel or otherwise, to any intellectual property rights is granted by or in connection with this document. This document is subject to change without notice. Reincarnate has been financed with support from the European Commission. This document reflects only the view of the author(s) and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
CFREU	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
CSA	Cybersecurity Act
DMA	Digital Market Act
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSA	Digital Services Act
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ECtHR	European Court of Human Right
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
MR	Mixed Reality
NIS Directive	Directive 2016/1148 on Network and Information Systems
NIS2 Directive	Directive 2020/0359 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity, across the Union, repealing the Directive 2016/1148.
NLP	Natural Language Processing
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality
IMCO	EU Parliament Committee on the Internal Market and Consumer Protection
LIBE	EU Parliament Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs

Contents

1. Introduction.....	8
2. Ethical Requirements for Designing and Developing CORTEX ²	10
2.1. High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) guidelines on trustworthy AI.....	13
2.2. European Union Artificial Intelligence Act.....	16
2.3. Research Ethics in CORTEX ²	19
2.4. Ethical considerations for NLP	20
2.5. Ethical Guidelines for Developing XR	22
3. Privacy and data protection requirements	25
3.1. The fundamental right to privacy and data protection	26
3.2. Council of Europe Convention 108.....	32
3.3. General Data Protection Regulation.....	33
3.3.1. Processing of Personal Data in CORTEX ²	34
3.3.2. Data protection roles envisaged in CORTEX ²	34
3.3.3. Data Protection Principles	37
3.3.4. Data subject rights.....	39
3.4. Special categories of personal data.....	41
3.5. Additional requirements of the GDPR.....	42
3.6. XR data as biometric data	46
3.7. Processing of Biometric data in XR.....	47
4. The Cybersecurity Framework.....	49
4.1. The Cybersecurity Act	50
4.1.1. The Role of ENISA	51
4.1.2. Cybersecurity Certification Framework	52

4.2.	The NIS 2 Directive	55
4.3.	Cyber Resilience Act (CRA).....	58
5.	Requirements from ancillary EU legal framework	61
5.1.	Overview of the European Strategy for Data.....	62
5.2.	EU Data Governance Act	63
5.3.	The EU Data Act.....	64
5.4.	The Digital Services Package	65
5.5.	Labour Law in the European Union.....	67
6.	Conclusion	69
	Bibliography	72

1. Introduction

Extended reality (XR), the collective name for a spectrum of immersive technologies (e.g. augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality (MR), that blend and connect the real world with digital elements and virtual environments, has reached a significant turning point in its development and application. The rapid adoption of XR necessitates a careful approach to ensure that, just like with previous transformational technologies such as AI, the rapid development and adoption of XR do not overwhelm regulators, policymakers, users, and other relevant stakeholders. These concerns are based on the fact that knowledge about the capabilities and risks of XR technology is still unfolding.

XR technologies also process personal data, thereby generating increased privacy and security concerns. Lapses in how XR technologies are developed can endanger people and society in ways that might prove challenging to resolve or reverse. Consequently, considering legal and ethical requirements at the early stages of developing XR technologies could help prevent potential risks such technology might cause for individuals and society. For instance, XR technology is capable of perpetuating existing biases, enabling discrimination in the workplace or subjecting users to profiling. Hence, it is important to ensure that these immersive technologies are developed in a manner that guards against these flaws.

This deliverable is an inventory of the ethical and legal requirements that are relevant for the design and development of CORTEX² technology to ensure that both ethical and legal considerations are accounted for. The inventory provided in this deliverable offers a general overview of the ethical principles, legal frameworks and initial guidelines to drive the innovative combination of technologies in CORTEX², especially AI and XR. Chapter 2 of the deliverable focuses on the ethical concerns relevant to CORTEX² and deals with the various technical components of CORTEX² that have ethical implications, especially the AI and immersive components. The chapter also briefly describes why it is important to incorporate ethics in both AI and XR and why ethics differs from law. The ethical inventory is based on the pre-existing and well-researched ethical standards in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the developing ethical discussions on extended reality (XR) that are relevant in the EU.

Chapter 3 of the deliverable introduces the privacy and data protection requirements that are relevant for CORTEX², especially the AI and XR components. It discusses the fundamental right to privacy and the right to data protection within the context of European and EU law, with a primary focus on the processing of personal data envisaged in CORTEX². The chapter also introduces the various data protection roles, data protection principles and the rights of data subjects. These privacy and data protection requirements are based on the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Council of Europe Modernised Convention 108, the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and the Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union. Chapter 3 also offers insights into the processing of sensitive data, especially the processing of biometric data by immersive technologies and the risks associated with such processing. This chapter touches on the additional requirements of the GDPR that will contribute to the robustness of the technology, such as the data protection impact assessment (DPIA), data protection by design and by default, the appointment of data protection officers and the requirement to record processing activities.

Chapter 4 of the deliverable focuses on the EU legal framework on cybersecurity that is relevant for CORTEX². It should be noted that although the use cases of the technology have not yet been finalised, the pilots identified and the conceivable uses of CORTEX² in business, technical, industrial and social contexts already create a substantial likelihood of cybersecurity risks which should be addressed in line with EU cybersecurity legal framework. The relevant frameworks discussed in this chapter include the NIS2 Directive,¹ Cyber security Act,² and Cyber Resilience Act.³

It is pertinent to point out that there is no concrete legal framework in the EU specifically dedicated to immersive technologies. However, various existing and impending legal

¹ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) PE/32/2022/REV/2, OJ L 333, 27.12.2022.

² Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act) PE/86/2018/REV/1, OJ L 151, 7.6.2019.

³ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 COM/2022/454 final

instruments in the EU are worth looking into if immersive technologies are to be developed in line with the values and norms of the EU. Hence, Chapter 4 of the deliverable discusses the ancillary legal instruments relating to data governance, regulation of platforms, competition and the fundamental rights of employees. In no specific order of priority, the notable legal frameworks discussed in the chapter include the GDPR,⁴ the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act Proposal,⁵ the Data Act,⁶ the Data Governance Act,⁷ the Digital Services Act and Digital Market Act.⁸

2. Ethical Requirements⁹ for Designing and Developing CORTEX²

CORTEX² is being developed to include a range of technical features that rely on artificial intelligence for reconstructing facial images and carrying out natural language processing. The regulation of AI is a particularly controversial area at the moment, and it is important to have ethical guidelines that stir the development of these AI components, especially in the absence of a concrete EU legal framework. In addition, adopting these AI-driven XR solutions for use in the workplace adds a new dimension of ethical concerns about immersive technologies.¹⁰

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

⁵ Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain union legislative acts COM/2021/206 final.

⁶ Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act) COM/2022/68 final.

⁷ Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance (Data Governance Act) COM/2020/767 final.

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act); PE/30/2022/REV/1, OJ L 277, 27.10.2022; Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act) PE/17/2022/REV/, OJ L 265, 12.10.2022.

⁹ Regarding the ethical requirements for the AI components of CORTEX², an independent AI Ethics Advisor has been appointed by the consortium to facilitate the compliance of the project with the EC Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI. In line with task T4.1 of the project, KUL has identified the ethical requirements for trustworthy AI stipulated in the aforementioned ethics guidelines in deliverable D4.1. The ethics guidelines will be a primary basis for the assessment of ethical compliance in the project by the Independent Ethics Advisor, as well as the in-depth analysis of ethical requirements for the AI components of CORTEX² in task T4.2.

¹⁰ Yogesh K. Dwivedi and others, 'Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Emerging Challenges, Opportunities, and Agenda for Research, Practice and Policy' (2021) 57 International Journal of Information Management 101994; Praveen Kumar Reddy Maddikunta and others, 'Industry 5.0: A Survey on Enabling Technologies and Potential Applications' (2022) 26 Journal of Industrial Information Integration 100257.

Hence, it is pertinent to weigh the long-term and wider repercussions of the technology and ensure ethical considerations are accounted for in this innovative project, especially in the EU, where legal guidance on XR is evolving.

For instance, preserving the autonomy of XR users is an important ethical requirement to be taken into consideration in the design and development of CORTEX². This is based on the fact that concerns regarding the moral permissibility of nudging have become relevant in light of the ongoing digitalisation of the workplace.¹¹ This is especially problematic, given the advent of machine learning, where AI can identify behavioural patterns and analyse digital footprints to adapt the systems to a person's digital choice environment and make “desired” decisions more likely.¹² While the law has a significant role to play in addressing these kinds of challenges, the role of ethics cannot be overlooked. Both law and ethics are geared towards addressing ongoing and future effects of AI on individuals, and society, providing normative guidance, and introducing the appropriate rules and values for governing human action, determining constraints, structures and functions of social-technical systems that rely on artificial intelligence.¹³

However, in reality, law and ethics are different. To fully understand the role of ethics in the design and development of AI and XR technology like CORTEX², it is pertinent to first of all note that there is no single global approach or standard for ethics and that ethics differs from law in its function, especially when ethics is applied as an instrument of social and political order.¹⁴ Ethics lacks the enforceability that the law possesses, and ethics does not create legal rights or legal obligation to comply, and responsibility for non-compliance with ethical principles is non-existent.¹⁵ Ethical principles and values do not seek to displace law but are designed to function where the law is deficient.¹⁶ Ethics remains an indispensable tool for addressing the challenges

¹¹ Rebecca C. Ruehle, ‘The Moral Permissibility of Digital Nudging in the Workplace: Reconciling Justification and Legitimation’ [2023] *Business Ethics Quarterly* 1.

¹² *ibid.*

¹³ Giovanni Sartor, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights: Between Law and Ethics’ (2020) 27 *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law* 705.

¹⁴ Margarita Robles Carrillo, ‘Artificial Intelligence: From Ethics to Law’ (2020) 44 *Telecommunications Policy* 101937.

¹⁵ *ibid.* 6.

¹⁶ Paula Boddington, ‘Towards a Code of Ethics for Artificial Intelligence’ (Springer International Publishing 2017) <<http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-60648-4>> accessed 6 July 2023; see also, Carrillo (n 14) 6.

of AI that fall outside the purview of the law. For instance, ethics is useful for understanding and addressing critical questions in AI relating to human agency and moral responsibility.¹⁷ In addition, not all ethical values or principles can be translated into legal norms.¹⁸ For example, it is unclear how the ethical principle of “non-maleficence” can attain legal translation.¹⁹ For these reasons, it is pertinent to recognise and preserve the role of ethics in the design and development of AI systems, especially where law is absent or inadequate.

In the case of the immersive XR technologies envisaged in CORTEX², the rapid advancements in XR capabilities and the growing adoption of the technology in society create real ethical concerns because of the likely impact of XR on society if prudent steps are not taken towards meaningful regulation.²⁰ For instance, the harvesting of biometric data through XR technologies raises not only legal issues but also ethical issues about the use of these biometric data, like eye-tracking for neuromarketing campaigns.²¹ Hence, as noted in the preceding paragraph, where the law is absent or inadequate, ethics can prove useful to ensure the development of XR technology is done with due consideration of societal concerns. It is also pertinent to point out that although there may be some commonalities, overlap and similarities among the ethical codes developed across various initiatives within and outside the EU, ethics is not homogenous.²² Ethical conceptions vary depending on traditions, cultures, ideologies, systems and countries.²³ For instance, the EU is highly conscious of fundamental rights. Hence, the EU AI ethics guidelines are based on the fundamental rights approach.²⁴

In line with the foregoing, this section of the deliverable focuses on EU perspectives, with particular emphasis on the requirements of the guidelines on trustworthy AI as proposed by

¹⁷ *ibid* 11.

¹⁸ Carrillo (n 14) 7.

¹⁹ *ibid*.

²⁰ Louis Rosenberg, ‘Regulation of the Metaverse: A Roadmap: The Risks and Regulatory Solutions for Largescale Consumer Platforms.’, *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Virtual and Augmented Reality Simulations* (Association for Computing Machinery 2022) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3546607.3546611>> accessed 6 July 2023.

²¹ Alexander J. Kent and Doug Specht, *The Routledge Handbook of Geospatial Technologies and Society* (Taylor & Francis 2023).

²² Carrillo (n 14) 3.

²³ *ibid*.

²⁴ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019) Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>. Accessed 6 Jul 2023.

the EU High-level Expert Group, and the relevant considerations in the impending EU Artificial Intelligence Act that have been translated from these ethical guidelines. This section of the deliverable also highlights research ethics as a prerequisite for CORTEX². In addition, the ethical considerations and guidelines that are relevant to natural language processing (NLP) and XR are introduced in this section of the deliverable.

2.1. High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) guidelines on trustworthy AI

Part of the EU's strategy for AI is to ensure that the appropriate ethical and legal frameworks are based on the Union's values and consistent with the provisions of the Charter. This strategy includes insights on product liability, analysis of emerging challenges, stakeholder participation and the development of AI ethics guidelines, with an emphasis on making AI trustworthy, accountable, transparent and less prone to the risk of bias and error.²⁵ In line with this objective, the commission spurred the development of the AI ethics guidelines with input from the relevant stakeholders like companies, academic institutions and civil society.²⁶ The effort also took due consideration of the provisions of the Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union. The ethical guidelines were established to address issues such as the future of work, fairness, safety, security, social inclusion and algorithmic transparency.²⁷

According to the HLEG, a trustworthy AI must meet specific requirements throughout the life cycle of the AI system. Such AI systems designed and developed in the EU must be *lawful, ethical* and *robust*.²⁸ This implies that AI systems must comply with all relevant laws and regulations, ensure strict compliance with ethical principles and values and be imbued with social and technical robustness in order not to cause harm. It should be noted that these components are not independent of one another. Rather, it requires a combination of all three components to achieve trustworthy AI.

²⁵ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, The European Council, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions, Artificial Intelligence for Europe (COM 2018) 237.

²⁶ Communication from The Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and The Committee of the Regions A European strategy for data 2020. COM/2020/66 final

²⁷ *ibid.*

²⁸ High-Level Expert Group on AI, 'Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI' (2019).

The HLEG guidelines on trustworthy AI do not explicitly deal with the Lawful AI requirements, and the provisions of the guidelines cannot be construed as legal advice on how to comply with existing legal requirements.²⁹ Instead, the guidelines merely offer tremendous insight into how to engender and support efforts for *ethical* and *robust* AI beyond the scope of existing legal obligations.³⁰ Hence, the focus of this section of the deliverable will be on the requirements for ethical and robust AI, as demonstrated in the HLEG guidelines. The HLEG recognises four ethical principles rooted in fundamental rights that must be taken into consideration if AI systems are to be developed, deployed and used in a trustworthy manner.³¹ The four relevant principles are (1) Respect for autonomy, (2) prevention of harm, (3) fairness, (4) Explicability.

Respect for the freedom and autonomy of human beings remains one of the hallmarks of the fundamental rights upon which the EU is founded. Hence, it is pertinent to ensure that humans retain effective control and self-determination over themselves in their interaction with AI systems and that such AI systems respect human choice and do not subordinate, coerce, deceive, manipulate, condition or herd humans without justification.³² With regard to CORTEX², it is pertinent to ensure that the AI systems such as virtual assistants do not compromise human autonomy through one or more of the several kinds of obstacles to the exercise of individual self-determination like nudging, manipulation, paternalism etc.³³ For instance, users must be able to retain control over how they use the virtual assistants or whether they use the virtual assistants at all. In addition, it is important to develop the AI system in ways that avoid creating dependencies through attention-capturing techniques or imitation of human attributes in ways that could cause confusion between humans and AI.³⁴

The ethical principle of harm prevention or non-maleficence is geared toward protecting human dignity and the mental and physical integrity of the human person, with special attention to vulnerable groups such as children, persons with disabilities and others that have

²⁹ *ibid* 6.

³⁰ *ibid*.

³¹ *ibid*.

³² *ibid*.

³³ Arto Laitinen and Otto Sahlgren, 'AI Systems and Respect for Human Autonomy' (2021) 4 *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence* <<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frai.2021.705164>> accessed 6 July 2023.

³⁴ Montreal Declaration for Responsible Development of Artificial Intelligence (Université de Montréal, 2018)

historically been disadvantaged or are at risk of exclusion. This principle requires AI to be technically robust to prevent misuse of AI systems and guard against adverse effects resulting from information and power asymmetries between employers and employees, businesses and consumers or governments and citizens.³⁵ This principle is concerned with questions about safety, security, harm prevention and risk mitigation. In line with this principle, CORTEX² will benefit from making sufficient information available to users and ensuring high safety/ security standards that meet all three dimensions of safety regarding (i) external safety for their environment and users, (ii) reliability and internal robustness against threats like hacking etc, (iii) emotional safety in human-machine interactions.³⁶

According to the HLEG, ethical AI must account for both procedural and substantive forms of fairness. Substantive fairness entails a commitment to ensuring equal distribution of both the costs and benefits and making certain that individuals and groups are not subjected to unfair bias, discrimination and stigmatisation.³⁷ Procedural fairness is focused on the ability of affected persons to contest and seek remedies against the decisions made by AI systems and the humans operating such systems.³⁸ In addition, the principle of fairness also entails preventing the creation of new harms that are capable of undermining existing social structures and ensuring inclusion and diversity throughout the lifecycle of the AI system – from design until deployment. In the context of CORTEX², it is important to ensure that the NLP language models do not perpetuate existing social issues like discrimination or create new forms of societal harm.

In addition, for an AI system to be considered trustworthy, it must possess a certain level of explicability. This implies that the processes of the system need to be transparent, the capabilities and purpose of the AI system must be disclosed, and the decisions should be explainable to the persons affected directly and indirectly. Explicability makes it possible to

³⁵ *ibid.*

³⁶ Nikos Th. Nikolinakos, 'Ethical Principles for Trustworthy AI' in Nikos Th. Nikolinakos (ed), *EU Policy and Legal Framework for Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and Related Technologies - The AI Act* (Springer International Publishing 2023) 127 <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-27953-9_3> accessed 6 July 2023.

³⁷ *ibid.*

³⁸ *ibid.*

contest decisions of AI systems and their deployers or operators. Explicability can be supported by other measures such as traceability, audibility, and transparent communication of capabilities, and the level of explicability required depends on the context and consequences of erroneous or inaccurate results from the AI systems.³⁹ In the case of CORTEX², it is pertinent to implement measures to inform users of their interaction with the AI and the capabilities and limitations of the AI in use, especially where the use cases pose a risk of death, injury, damage or severe implications for the fundamental rights of individuals.

Hence, the HLEG ethical guidelines are relevant for the CORTEX² project because of the emphasis on developing the CORTEX² framework with due consideration for the relevant ethical requirements. In furtherance of the guidelines of the HLEG, seven specific requirements in the form of an assessment checklist for trustworthy AI (ALTAI) have been introduced, they include (1) human agency and oversight, (2) technical robustness and safety, (3) privacy and data governance, (4) transparency (5) diversity, non-discrimination and fairness (6) societal and environmental wellbeing (7) Accountability. The concrete analysis of these relevant specific requirements for CORTEX² identified will be conducted in the subsequent deliverable D4.2. In addition, it is pertinent to mention that some of these specific requirements, like technical robustness and safety, have begun to make their way into upcoming legislation at the EU level, such as the impending European Artificial Intelligence Act proposal, which is discussed in the next subsection.

2.2. European Union Artificial Intelligence Act

Although the EU Ethics Guidelines for AI is still the prevailing instrument driving the design and development of AI systems in the EU, the impending EU AI Act proposal is relevant for the AI-driven components of CORTEX², especially NLP. The relevant provisions will be introduced to ensure that CORTEX² is developed in a manner that is consistent with the provisions of the EU AI Act by incorporating acceptable levels of transparency, accuracy, human oversight and understandability. The in-depth analysis of these provisions on transparency, accuracy, human

³⁹ *ibid.*

oversight and understandability will be conducted in subsequent deliverable D4.2 especially the accuracy requirements for AI models used in NLP in CORTEX².

Although the EU AI Act is not yet a done deal, it is a vital piece of legislation that will set the tone for the development of AI in the coming years. The EU AI Act is the first comprehensive legal framework on Artificial Intelligence, and since its first publication in April 2021, the Act has gone through a series of appraisals and adjustments in order to arrive at a comprehensive set of laws for the regulation of AI. As of April 2023, the EU lawmakers have passed the draft of the AI Act, and this spells interesting times for the development of AI systems that will be placed within the EU internal market as the impending legislation makes its way into the trilogue stage where member states and the EU parliament will hash out the final details of the bill. The subsequent deliverable D4.2 will address any relevant progress in the trajectory of the proposal that is relevant for CORTEX².

The impending legal framework digs into the design, development and deployment of AI systems using a risk-based approach. This implies that the requirements and classification of AI systems are based on the perceived risks of such AI systems, including (1) unacceptable risk, (2) high risk, (3) limited risk (4) minimal risk. There is a challenge in classifying the generative AI models in NLP using a risk-based approach, given that the EU AI Act was originally intended for traditional AI systems, unlike generative AI, and also because “generative AI systems are not built for specific context or conditions of use, and their openness and ease of control allow for an unprecedented scale of use.”⁴⁰ For instance, the recent incidents with ChatGpt indicate that generative AI can be abused for malicious purposes like disinformation and harmful content creation, and this has made regulators reconsider what should constitute high-risk systems and how generative AI systems should be regulated.⁴¹

However, on May 11 2023, the European Parliament Committee on the Internal Market and Consumer Protection (IMCO) and the Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs

⁴⁰ Natali Helberger and Nicholas Diakopoulos, ‘ChatGPT and the AI Act’ (2023) 12 Internet Policy Review <<https://policyreview.info/essay/chatgpt-and-ai-act>> accessed 4 June 2023.

⁴¹ Ibid; Gian Volpicelli, ‘ChatGPT Broke the EU Plan to Regulate AI’ (*POLITICO*, 3 March 2023) <<https://www.politico.eu/article/eu-plan-regulate-chatgpt-openai-artificial-intelligence-act/>> accessed 24 July 2023.

(LIBE) adopted the draft report on the AI Act, which includes important amendments and additions to what can be classified as high-risk systems. With this vote, amendment 297 of the draft report introduces new language that can accommodate generative AI, to wit;⁴²

“(a) AI systems intended to be used to generate, on the basis of limited human input, complex text content that would falsely appear to a person to be human-generated and authentic, such as news articles, opinion articles, novels, scripts, and scientific articles;

(b) AI systems intended to be used to generate or manipulate audio or video content that appreciably resembles existing natural persons, in a manner that significantly distorts or fabricates the original situation, meaning, content, or context and would falsely appear to a person to be authentic.”

In light of the foregoing, it is pertinent for CORTEX² to ensure that the provisions of the EU AI Act are given due consideration in the design and development of the framework because of the capability of CORTEX² to generate avatars that are identical to existing natural persons and create virtual copies of real-world environments and scenarios. Some of the most relevant provisions to be considered include; requirements regarding prohibited AI practices like (1) the use of subliminal techniques;⁴³ (2) the requirement to produce technical documentation before the AI is placed on the market; such documentation must demonstrate compliance with the requirement of the regulation;⁴⁴ (3) data and data governance requirements regarding training, validation and testing of data sets.⁴⁵ (4) record keeping⁴⁶ , (5) transparency⁴⁷ and providing

⁴² Committee on the Internal Market and Consumer Protection Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs, amendment 297, Draft Report on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union Legislative Acts (COM2021/0206 – C9-0146/2021 – 2021/0106(COD)).

⁴³ Article 5 AI Act proposal.

⁴⁴ Article 11 AI Act proposal .

⁴⁵ Article 10 AI Act proposal.

⁴⁶ Article 12 AI Act proposal.

⁴⁷ Article 13 AI Act proposal.

information to users, (6) human oversight⁴⁸, (7) Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity.⁴⁹ Besides these requirements, there are also obligations for providers of high-risk AI systems in Chapter 3 of the proposal, such as conformity assessments, taking corrective actions and cooperation with competent authorities.⁵⁰ These requirements and obligations will be critically analysed in relation to CORTEX² in deliverable D4.2 and recommendations will be formulated based on this analysis.

2.3. Research Ethics in CORTEX²

The research activities envisaged in CORTEX² must be carried out with the utmost regard for ethical principles relating to the research activities conducted in the course of the development of CORTEX². This implies compliance with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity Guidelines regarding reliability of research, honesty, respect and accountability.⁵¹ The research efforts in the project must also respect the ethical principles recognised in various supra-national and national laws throughout the lifecycle of the project, such as the Charter and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.⁵² With regard to CORTEX², some of the overlapping ethical issues identified include the involvement of human participants in non-medical research, especially the use cases that will be used to evaluate the technological solutions developed in the course of CORTEX². In addition, there are concerns about the possible misuse of the research, such as the use of virtual environments for illicit or dangerous activities, and any possible negative societal impact of the technology developed in the course of the research.

The Ethical self-assessment conducted in CORTEX² indicates that human subjects will be involved in the use cases developed for the three pilots of the project to evaluate the technological solutions developed in the course of CORTEX². In this case, the project partners

⁴⁸ Article 14 AI Act proposal.

⁴⁹ Article 15 AI Act proposal.

⁵⁰ Articles 19, 21 and 23 AI Act proposal.

⁵¹ See ALLEA, The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Revised Edition, 2017, last accessed on 23 May 2023.

⁵² Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013, Article 19.

must ensure respect for the individual and human dignity and fair distribution of the benefits and burden of research as well as the protection of the values, rights and interests of the research participants.⁵³

2.4. Ethical considerations for NLP

One of the objectives of CORTEX² is to develop a conversational agent or virtual assistant based on NLP. The innovative use of NLP envisaged in CORTEX² raises ethical issues which must be mitigated by implementing ethical requirements in the course of the project. Given the proposed use of the technology, some of the relevant ethical principles for the NLP components of CORTEX² are autonomy and non-manipulation, fairness and freedom from bias, respect, responsibility, safety and transparency. These ethical requirements are discussed below.

Autonomy remains a core ethical principle in the field of applied ethics, especially concerning AI.⁵⁴ This is because of the potential influence of Algorithmic techniques on an individual's autonomy and decision-making processes.⁵⁵ "An autonomous choice is a choice between potential courses of action that cannot be casual, that is, that cannot result from factors out of control of the agent".⁵⁶ In other words, human agents must be able to exercise self-determination and self-governance and choose and act according to beliefs, values, motives, and reasons, even in the face of algorithmic systems like conversational agents or virtual assistants. However, the profiling and predictive power of algorithmic agents have the potential to create "*choice architectures*" capable of reshaping the social, environmental, and structural fabrics of our informational societies. Meaning that they can change how we interact, perceive reality, and understand each other and ourselves and take action.⁵⁷

Choice architecture refers to the algorithmic capability to curate what qualifies as meaningful information without the active participation of human agents, thereby limiting the options

⁵³ European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, "Horizon 2020 Programme Guidance: How to complete your ethics self-assessment", Version 6.1, 23 May 2023.

⁵⁴ Gianluigi Riva and Simona Tiribelli, 'Moral and Legal Autonomy in the Era of Artificial Intelligence' (S&F_scienzae filosofia.it 2022).

⁵⁵ *ibid.*

⁵⁶ *ibid.*

⁵⁷ *ibid.*

available in any given situation.⁵⁸ When these algorithmic systems are adopted by institutional actors, such as in the context of employment, they can be used to alter the informational environment of employees to influence and predictably change their behaviour without necessarily depriving them of the right to choose. It is pertinent to ensure that the conversational agents in CORTEX² do not compromise the ethical principle of human autonomy.

In addition, the use of NLP processing must be done in a way that ensures freedom from bias. This is based on the fact that biased NLP models have far-reaching consequences on everyday life, especially given the rapid adoption of the technology.⁵⁹ For instance, NLP applications lead to consequences like unfairness resulting from demographic biases, like misidentification of speakers and their needs, the proliferation of harmful stereotypes and producing unequal results for different user groups.⁶⁰ Hence, CORTEX² must pay attention to all the possible sources of bias in NLP, including bias from data sets used in training the models, bias from annotations, bias from input representations, bias from models and bias from research design.⁶¹ NLP systems should be accessible and inclusive to every community group or individual to ensure that the systems do not perpetuate social injustices or marginalise vulnerable groups.⁶²

Developing a safe and ethical language model for NLP remains a crucial challenge for developing responsible Artificial Intelligence. This is particularly relevant when NLP is used in high-stakes decision-making like healthcare, education, finance, and criminal justice.⁶³ NLP systems must be designed and developed in a manner that does not pose unreasonably high safety risks, and the safety measures should be appropriate to the size of potential threats.⁶⁴

⁵⁸ *ibid.*

⁵⁹ Dirk Hovy and Shrimai Prabhumoye, 'Five Sources of Bias in Natural Language Processing' (2021) 15 *Language and Linguistics Compass* e12432.

⁶⁰ *ibid.*

⁶¹ *ibid.*

⁶² Rajat Kumar Behera and others, 'Responsible Natural Language Processing: A Principlist Framework for Social Benefits' (2023) 188 *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 122306.

⁶³ Andreas Madsen, Siva Reddy, and Sarath Chandar, 'Post-Hoc Interpretability for Neural NLP: A Survey' (2022) 55 *ACM Computing Surveys* 155:1.v

⁶⁴ Behera and others (n 58).

For instance, conversational agents are susceptible to prompt injections that allow for the bypass of safety features in order to generate dangerous, immoral or illegal responses.⁶⁵

Transparency is another fundamental ethical principle that is relevant for the development of NLP. Transparency in the NLP system should ensure responsible disclosure to enable the users to recognise when NLP is having a substantial influence on them.⁶⁶ These responsible disclosures should be done promptly, and reasonable justifications must be offered for the results of the NLP systems.

Accountability is an ethical principle that is relevant for NLP because it seeks to entrench human oversight in NLP to ensure that those responsible for the various phases of the lifecycle of NLP systems are identifiable and can be held to account for the results produced by the NLP systems. The ethical principle of accountability will help to ensure that the relevant organisations or individuals bear the responsibility for the consequences produced by the NLP systems they design, build, deploy and operate.⁶⁷ The concrete analysis of these ethical requirements, their relevance and role in CORTEX², and recommendations will be discussed in the subsequent deliverable D4.2.

2.5. Ethical Guidelines for Developing XR

Managing XR systems and the behaviour of the users of the ecosystem has been a long-standing challenge dating back to the 1960s, and these problems have remained to date.⁶⁸ The governance issue stems from product design, data control and privacy concerns, and the failure to enforce industry standards.⁶⁹ There is also no comprehensive legal framework regulating XR and many of the risks associated with the technology. In the absence of a comprehensive EU-wide legal framework for the design, development and deployment of XR, it is pertinent to rely

⁶⁵ Terry Yue Zhuo and others, 'Exploring AI Ethics of ChatGPT: A Diagnostic Analysis' (arXiv, 22 February 2023) <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2301.12867>> accessed 24 May 2023.

⁶⁶ Behera and others (n 58).

⁶⁷ *ibid*; Buomsoo Kim, Jinsoo Park, and Jihae Suh, 'Transparency and Accountability in AI Decision Support: Explaining and Visualizing Convolutional Neural Networks for Text Information' (2020) 134 *Decision Support Systems* 113302.

⁶⁸ Melodena Stephens Balakrishnan and others, 'Metaverse and Its Governance - The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report' <https://standards.ieee.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/XR_Metaverse_Governance.pdf> accessed 5 June 2023

⁶⁹ *ibid*.

on ethical considerations. CORTEX² will be tested across a range of use cases based on the already identified pilots, business meetings, industrial production and remote training. Although the specific use cases are not yet determined, relying on the Ethical Self-assessment toolkit and academic literature, it is already possible to identify some cross-cutting ethical issues that should be considered in the development of XR technology, such as transparency, trust, safety, responsibility, autonomy, nudging and non-manipulation, dual use and misuse of technology, diversity, inclusion and accessibility.⁷⁰ The implication of these ethical concerns for the XR components of CORTEX² will be discussed in subsequent deliverable D4.2, as well as possible recommendations.

It is of utmost importance to ensure that safety issues arising from the use of XR in the workplace are addressed in order to prevent physical or non-physical harm to users of CORTEX². Various malicious scenarios can occur in XR that could lead to a dangerous environment for both the user and those around them. For instance, there can be serious injuries and serious consequences when XR is misused in industrial environments that are prone to accidents.⁷¹ Care must also be taken to ensure that the XR does not create a malicious or unsafe environment for vulnerable users, such as an unsafe lighting experience in the virtual environment for epileptic users.⁷² It is also pertinent to point out that in the case of CORTEX², where multiple entities are responsible for designing and developing various aspects of the framework, it is important to think deeply about the safety implications of CORTEX². Safety concerns are also relevant for the accessibility of the data collected or insights inferred from collected data sets.⁷³

⁷⁰ Dylan Fox and Isabel Guenette Thornton, 'The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Extended Reality (XR) Ethics and Diversity, Inclusion, and Accessibility' [2022] The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Extended Reality (XR) Ethics and Diversity, Inclusion, and Accessibility 1; European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, "Horizon 2020 Programme Guidance: How to complete your ethics self-assessment", Version 6.1, 23 May 2023.

⁷¹ Suchismita Pahi and Calli Schroeder, 'Extended Privacy for Extended Reality: XR Technology Has 99 Problems and Privacy Is Several of Them' (28 August 2022) <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=4202913>> accessed 5 June 2023.

⁷² Melvin Abraham and others, 'Implications of XR on Privacy, Security and Behaviour: Insights from Experts', *Nordic Human-Computer Interaction Conference* (ACM 2022) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3546155.3546691>> accessed 8 June 2023.

⁷³ Suchismita Pahi and Calli Schroeder, 'Extended Privacy for Extended Reality: XR Technology Has 99 Problems and Privacy Is Several of Them' (28 August 2022) <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=4202913>> accessed 9 June 2023.

Summary of ethical requirements:

<p>The following ethical requirements have been identified as relevant for the XR components of CORTEX². The requirements are explained in Chapter 2 of this deliverable and will be further analysed in-depth, in task T4.2.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Autonomy 2. Fairness 3. Freedom from bias, 4. Safety 5. Transparency. 	<p>The ethical requirements relevant to the AI components of CORTEX² are based on the HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trust Worthy Artificial Intelligence introduced in section 2.1 of this chapter, namely:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Human Agency and Oversight 2. Technical Robustness and Safety 3. Privacy and Data Governance 4. Transparency 5. Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness 6. Societal and Environmental Well-being 7. Accountability
---	--

<p>Recommendation 1</p>	<p>In this section the following ethical requirements/concerns were identified as relevant for CORTEX²: respect for human autonomy, trust, transparency, safety, responsibility, fairness and freedom from bias, diversity, inclusion and accessibility, Although the concrete analysis of the ethical considerations in D4.2 will form the basis for the main recommendations in the project, some initial recommendations to the technical partners can be made on the basis of this inventory, such as the use of good quality data sets for training the AI models in</p>
--------------------------------	--

	<p>CORTEX² to prevent bias or other forms of unwanted results.</p> <p>It is pertinent for CORTEX² to think ahead about the safety issues as use cases are being formulated in the course of the project in order to identify ways of ensuring the safety of users in both the virtual environment and physical environments.</p>
--	--

3. Privacy and data protection requirements

The main objective of CORTEX² is to develop an open, versatile, inclusive and scalable digital workplace using a range of technical modules, including instantaneous 3D modelling of surroundings, interactive avatars, speech recognition, automatic text summarization and tracking non-verbal communication and gestures.⁷⁴ The technical modules envisaged in CORTEX² involve the processing of special categories of personal data, such as voices, behaviours, gestures, and facial images, and this type of processing can only be allowed under the strict requirements imposed by privacy and data protection laws. Hence, this section of the deliverable introduces the legal frameworks that will form the basis for the privacy and data protection requirements to be implemented in the design and development of CORTEX².

The legal instruments discussed in this section of the deliverable include the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (the Charter), the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (CETS No. 108) (Modernised Convention 108), and the GDPR. This section highlights the requirements for the fundamental right to privacy pursuant to the Charter as well as the relevant aspects of the right to data protection under the GDPR, such as the principles of data protection, the right of data subjects

⁷⁴ CORTEX2, 'Project' <<https://cortex2.eu/project/>> accessed 3 June 2023.

and the various legal obligations imposed on data controllers and processors by the GDPR. It is pertinent to introduce these privacy and data protection concepts at this stage of CORTEX² to ensure that they are taken into consideration from the beginning of the project.

To give a proper overview of the privacy and data protection requirements envisaged in CORTEX² this chapter of the deliverable discusses the fundamental right to privacy entrenched in the Charter, particularly the requirements for limiting the right to privacy. This is followed by a brief overview of two salient legal instruments governing the right to data protection, the Modernised Convention 108 and the GDPR, with greater emphasis on the provisions of the GDPR. This chapter also introduces the key elements of the right to data protection that will form the basis for future analysis of CORTEX². The key elements referred to are the roles of important actors like data controllers and processors, data protection principles, data subject rights, special categories of personal data and other additional requirements like Data Protection Impact Assessments and the role of the data protection officers and recording of processing activities. This chapter of the deliverable also introduces the discussion about biometric data in XR technology.

3.1. The fundamental right to privacy and data protection

The fundamental right to privacy, which is also referred to in European law as the right to respect for private life, can be traced to the Universal Declaration of human rights, which was adopted in 1948.⁷⁵ The fundamental right to privacy was reaffirmed in the European Convention on Human Rights and is legally binding on the contracting parties. The ECHR provides that everyone is entitled to the right to respect for their private and family life, home and correspondence and derogation from this right by a public authority is prohibited unless where such interference is backed by law, in pursuit of important and legitimate public interests and is deemed necessary in a democratic society.⁷⁶ It is pertinent to state that the right to data protection is part of the rights protected under the fundamental right to privacy as provided in Article 8 ECHR, and these rights have now been incorporated into the Charter of Fundamental

⁷⁵ Christos Giakoumopoulos, Giovanni Buttarelli, and Michael O'Flaherty, 'Handbook on European Data Protection Law 2018 Edition' (2018).

⁷⁶ Article 8 ECHR; Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O'Flaherty (n 75) 18.

Rights of the European Union (the Charter) as two distinct rights. The lack of specific provisions for data protection in the ECHR has been remedied by the Council of Europe’s Convention 108 on the processing of personal data and the subsequent amendment modernising the convention.

The Charter of Fundamental Rights is the European Union’s bill of human rights which entered into force with the Treaty of Lisbon on 1 December 2009.⁷⁷ The Charter applies to EU institutions, bodies, offices and agencies, and Member states, all of whom are mandated to respect the rights guaranteed by the Charter when implementing EU law. The Charter applies in conjunction with national and international fundamental rights protection systems, including the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). The Charter guarantees the respect for private and family life in Article 7 and establishes the right to protection of personal data pursuant to Article 8 of the Charter, thereby elevating these protections to the level of fundamental rights in EU law.⁷⁸

Both the ECHR and the Charter stipulate the grounds under which respect for private life and the right to personal data protection may be limited, and these grounds have been developed and interpreted through the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) and the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU).⁷⁹ Article 8(2) ECHR provides that: “There shall be no interference by a public authority with the exercise of this right except such an is in accordance with the law and is necessary in a democratic society in the interests of national security, public safety or the economic well-being of the country, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others”. A similar provision is contained in Article 52(1) of the Charter which stipulates that “any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by this Charter must be

⁷⁷ Allan Rosas, ‘The Court of Justice of the European Union: A Human Rights Institution?’ (2022) 14 *Journal of Human Rights Practice* 204; The Charter consists of seven chapters: Chapter I contains the provisions on Dignity, Freedoms is provided for in Chapter II, Equality and Solidarity are discussed in chapter III and IV respectively, Citizens’ rights is contained in Chapter V of the charter while Justice and the general provision are dealt with in Chapter VI and VII respectively.

⁷⁸ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 28; Article 8 ECHR; Article 52(1) the Charter.

⁷⁹ ECtHR, *S. and Marper v. the United Kingdom* [GC], Nos. 30562/04 and 30566/04, 8 December 2008; *Volker und Markus Schecke GbR and Hartmut Eifert v. Land Hessen* [GC], 9 November 2010, para. 50; Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 36.

provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms. Subject to the principle of proportionality, limitations may be made only if they are necessary and genuinely meet objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others”.

From the foregoing, it is clear that under the ECHR, interference with the right to respect for private life is only permissible where it is carried out: (1) in accordance with the law, (2) pursues a legitimate aim, (3) respects the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms (4) is necessary and proportionate in a democratic society to achieve a legitimate purpose. The EU legal order (the Charter) has a similar set of requirements to justify imposing limitations on the fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter, and such interference must (1) be in accordance with the law, (2) respect the essence of the right, (3) be subject to the principle of proportionality and necessity, (4) pursue an objective of general interest recognised by the EU, or the need to protect the rights of others.

For interference to be justified under the ECHR, it is important to determine whether a person’s private life has been compromised, and the term “private life” has been given a broad interpretation to include aspects of professional life and public behaviour.⁸⁰ In addition, pursuant to the decision of the (CJEU), it is established law in the EU that the fundamental right to privacy extends to the workplace and employment. However, interference is determined on a case-by-case basis.⁸¹ The foundation of the fundamental rights of privacy aims to protect the sanctity of private and family life, the home and the correspondence of an individual.⁸² The right to data protection is mainly concerned with operations involving the processing of personal data regardless of the impact of such processing on privacy.⁸³

⁸⁰ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 37.

⁸¹ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 20; CJEU, Joined cases C-293/12 and C-594/12, *Digital Rights Ireland Ltd v. Minister for Communications, Marine and Natural Resources and Others and Kärntner Landesregierung and Others* [GC], 8 April 2014.

⁸² Oliver Diggelmann and Maria Nicole Cleis, ‘How the Right to Privacy Became a Human Right’ (2014) 14 *Human Rights Law Review* 441.

⁸³ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) ch1; Article 4(2) GDPR.

Before pointing out the relevance of these provisions to CORTEX², it is pertinent to stipulate that although the ECHR and the Charter have different wordings regarding the conditions for lawful limitations or interference, both the ECtHR and the CJEU refer to each other's judgments in a bid to achieve a harmonious interpretation of privacy and data protection rules. This position is given further credence by Article 52(3) of the Charter, which provides that "in so far as this Charter contains rights which correspond to rights guaranteed by the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the meaning and scope of those rights shall be the same as those laid down by the said Convention."

Hence, the design, development and adoption of the XR solutions for work and social use that interferes with the private life, home and correspondence of an individual must comply with the provisions of the ECHR and the Charter.⁸⁴ In line with this submission, CORTEX² must be designed and developed in a manner that satisfies the provisions of Article 8(2) ECHR regarding the permissible grounds for interfering with the fundamental right to privacy as well as the provisions of Article 52(1) regarding lawful limitation on the rights enshrined in the Charter. To this end, CORTEX² must be in accordance with the law, in pursuit of a legitimate aim, respect the essence of fundamental rights and freedoms, and be necessary and proportional in a democratic society to achieve a legitimate purpose.⁸⁵ Pursuant to Article 52(1) of the Charter, CORTEX² must ensure that any limitations on the fundamental rights guaranteed by the Charter must be (1) in accordance with the law, (2) respect the essence of the right, (3) be subject to the principle of proportionality and be necessary (4) pursue an objective of general interest that is recognised by the EU, or the need to protect the rights of others.

These privacy requirements imply that CORTEX² must derive legitimacy from the existing national or EU legal framework, which provides the requisite legal basis for interference with the fundamental right to privacy. CORTEX² will be used in the context of employment, and it is important for such interference not to be done arbitrarily because of the potential consequences for privacy and data protection. There needs to be a legal basis that is adequately

⁸⁴ Article 8 ECHR ; Article 7 the Charter.

⁸⁵ Article 8(2) ECHR, Article 52(1) the Charter; ECtHR, *S. and Marper v. the United Kingdom* [GC], Nos. 30562/04 and 30566/04, 4 December 2008; CJEU, *Joined cases C-92/09 and C-93/09, Volker und Markus Schecke GbR and Hartmut Eifert v. Land Hessen* [GC], 9 November 2010.

accessible and foreseeable and formulated with sufficient precision to ensure that individuals (e.g. employees) can understand their obligations and regulate their conduct.⁸⁶

In addition, the technology development in CORTEX² must respect the essence of the fundamental rights protected in the Charter. In practical terms, this implies that any limitation on the right to privacy that is deemed too extensive and intrusive and capable of undermining the fundamental right is deemed unjustifiable and unlawful.⁸⁷ For instance, the retention period of data in CORTEX² should be reasonable, and granting access to the data in CORTEX² should be justifiable.⁸⁸ Irrespective of whether the interference serves an objective of general interest, is necessary and proportional, it would be deemed unlawful where the essence of the fundamental rights is not respected.⁸⁹

The necessity requirement in the Charter means that interference with the fundamental right to privacy must be strictly necessary, in that sense that the measures sought to be applied must be less intrusive in comparison to the other possible measures for achieving the aim pursued.⁹⁰ CORTEX² intends to design and develop “novel technical modules” that will transform traditional videoconferencing and facilitate cooperative work. It is pertinent to ensure that any resulting interference with the right to privacy is strictly necessary for the aim pursued.

Once the necessity test has been conducted, the proportionality assessment becomes the next step. Pursuant to the proportionality test, derogations from the fundamental right to privacy are permissible where the advantage sort to be obtained from the interference with the right to privacy outweighs the disadvantages accruing from such interference.⁹¹ However, in order to reduce the disadvantages and risks to the right to privacy and data protection, it is important

⁸⁶ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 43.

⁸⁷ *ibid* 44; CJEU, Joined cases C-293/12 and C-594/12, *Digital Rights Ireland Ltd v. Minister for Communications, Marine and Natural Resources and Others and Kärntner Landesregierung and Others* [GC], 8 April 2014.

⁸⁸ CJEU, C-362/14, *Maximillian Schrems v. Data Protection Commissioner* [GC], 6 October 2015; CJEU, Joined cases C-293/12 and C-594/12, *Digital Rights Ireland Ltd v. Minister for Communications, Marine and Natural Resources and Others and Kärntner Landesregierung and Others* [GC], 8 April 2014.

⁸⁹ *Digital Rights Ireland Ltd v. Minister for Communications, Marine and Natural Resources and Others and Kärntner Landesregierung and Others* [GC], 8 April 2014.

⁹⁰ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 46; Article 52(1) the Charter.

⁹¹ Article 52(1) the Charter; European Data Protection Supervisor (2017), *Necessity Toolkit*, 5.

to ensure that the limitations are not applied without any form of safeguards in place.⁹² In the case of CORTEX2, the appropriate analysis will be conducted in subsequent deliverable D4.2 to ensure that the advantages sought to be obtained from the processing activities in the pilots and use cases, including the processing of sensitive data,⁹³ outweighs the disadvantages and risks to the right to privacy and data protection. The technical and organisational safeguards implemented will also be analysed for adequacy in the subsequent deliverables.

The final test is the requirement to justify any limitation on the exercise of the rights recognised by the charter by ensuring that such limitation meets objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of other persons.⁹⁴ This includes national security and defence, the prevention of crime, the preservation of important economic and financial interests of the EU or Member States, for public health and social security.⁹⁵

Recommendation 2

Considering that the Charter explicitly raises the level of personal data protection to that of a fundamental right in EU law, the design and deployment of the CORTEX² project shall consider the rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Charter, specifically the protection of personal data. In addition, the individual “novel technical modules” should be evaluated for compliance with these privacy and data protection requirements.

⁹² Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 46.

⁹³ Pursuant to Article 9 GDPR, Sensitive data are special categories of personal data that reveal racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, this category also includes genetic data, biometric data, health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation. See Section 3.4 of this deliverable.

⁹⁴ Article 52(1) the Charter; Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 48.

⁹⁵ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 48.

3.2. Council of Europe Convention 108

The Council of Europe Convention for the Protection of Individuals concerning the automatic processing of personal data has been in effect since 1985 and is still open for signatures.⁹⁶ Its purpose is to ensure that individuals' rights and fundamental freedoms, especially the right to privacy, are protected when it comes to the automatic processing of personal data.⁹⁷ The Convention applies to data processing carried out by both the public and private sectors, including by the judiciary and law enforcement authorities. Convention 108 was the first and only legally binding international instrument in the data protection field. It was established in 1982 and has a broader reach than the GDPR, allowing non-European countries to become State Parties.⁹⁸ Currently, 55 countries are party to Convention 108, and each Party State is required to apply the Convention to data processing under its jurisdiction in the public and private sectors and take appropriate measures to give effect to the provisions of the Convention.⁹⁹ It is worth noting that Convention 108 is binding for states that have ratified it, and the Convention is not subject to the judicial supervision of the ECtHR. Nevertheless, it has been taken into account in ECtHR case law within the context of Article 8 of the ECHR.

Convention 108 underwent significant modernization in 2018 to address privacy challenges stemming from new technologies and strengthen its enforcement, including changing the name to Convention 108+.¹⁰⁰ It should be noted that the provisions of the Modernised Convention 108 are consistent with the provisions of the GDPR. The Modernised Convention 108 is relevant for the development of CORTEX² because of its technological neutrality and specific protection for individual rights to protection of personal data in the contracting member states (beyond the EU), as opposed to the mere right to private life provided for in the ECHR. This makes it a useful instrument for setting future global privacy standards in XR design

⁹⁶ Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CETS No. 108, 1981.

⁹⁷ Article 1 Modernised Convention 108.

⁹⁸ T. Mulder and M. Tudorica, 'Privacy Policies, Cross-Border Health Data and the GDPR' (2019) 28 Information & Communications Technology Law 261.

⁹⁹ Apart from 47 Council of Europe Member States, Convention applies to Uruguay, Mauritius, Senegal, Tunisia, Cabo Verde, Mexico, Argentina and Morocco.

¹⁰⁰ The amending Protocol (CETS No. 223) to Convention 108 was adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on 18 May 2018 on the occasion of its 128th session held in Elsinore, Denmark.

and development.¹⁰¹ Although the Modernised Convention 108 recognises the same principles of data protection enshrined in the GDPR, the data protection requirements stemming from the GDPR remain the main focus of this inventory and the basis for the concrete legal analysis of the privacy and data protection requirements that will be addressed in deliverable D4.2.

In addition, the Modernised Convention 108 is also relevant for CORTEX² because it prioritises the protection of human dignity and personal autonomy when processing personal data.¹⁰² Respecting human dignity and personal autonomy in the design of CORTEX² can contribute to protecting the rights and fundamental freedoms associated with these values, such as the right to non-discrimination and the right to privacy.¹⁰³

3.3. General Data Protection Regulation

The GDPR is an important piece of legislation at the EU level which stipulates the rules pertaining to the processing of the personal data of natural persons and the free movement of personal data.¹⁰⁴ The regulation seeks to ensure that natural persons enjoy the right to data protection where the processing of personal data is conducted regardless of whether such data processing is carried out by automated means.¹⁰⁵

Given the nature of the CORTEX² technology, most notably the AI and XR components, the impending processing operations involve various categories of personal data, including biometric and behavioural data required to facilitate the CORTEX² framework. These processing activities bring the project within the scope of the GDPR. Hence, it is pertinent to determine the various categories of personal data implicated in the processing activities and the operations that are subject to the GDPR in a bid to ensure that the CORTEX² framework is designed and developed in line with the dictates of the GDPR.

¹⁰¹ Alessandro Mantelero, 'The Future of Data Protection: Gold Standard vs. Global Standard' (2021) 40 Computer Law & Security Review 105500.

¹⁰² Preamble to the Modernized Convention 108; see also, Cécile de Terwangne, 'Council of Europe Convention 108+: A Modernised International Treaty for the Protection of Personal Data' (2021) 40 Computer Law & Security Review 105497.

¹⁰³ de Terwangne, (n 102).

¹⁰⁴ Article 1(1) GDPR.

¹⁰⁵ Article 1(2) & Article 2(1) GDPR.

3.3.1. Processing of Personal Data in CORTEX²

As CORTEX² involves various processing activities, such as the processing of facial images, behaviour and voices, it is pertinent to note the definition of processing as stipulated in the GDPR. According to the GDPR, data processing "means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction."¹⁰⁶

It is also pertinent to pay attention to the possibility of cross-border processing of personal data in the context of the CORTEX² project. Specifically, where the architecture or components of CORTEX² technology creates a likelihood of cross-border processing of personal data, attention must be given to ensure this is done in accordance with the provisions of the GDPR. According to the GDPR, cross-border processing' means either "processing of personal data which takes place in the context of the activities of establishments in more than one Member State of a controller or processor in the Union where the controller or processor is established in more than one Member State" or "processing of personal data which takes place in the context of the activities of a single establishment of a controller or processor in the Union but which substantially affects or is likely to substantially affect data subjects in more than one Member State."¹⁰⁷

Since the GDPR recognises cross-border processing of personal data, this is also relevant for the CORTEX² project as various components of CORTEX² will be designed and supported by various partners located in various EU member states, and these components will be used to further develop additional platforms following an open call for use cases across the EU.

3.3.2. Data protection roles envisaged in CORTEX²

CORTEX² involves a complex web of processing activities. Hence, it is pertinent to understand the roles recognised by the GDPR in detail and determine how the obligations created by the

¹⁰⁶ Article 4(2) GDPR.

¹⁰⁷ Article 4 (23) GDPR.

GDPR apply to the various actors/partners in the project. The roles to be discussed are the data controller, joint controllers, processors, and recipients.

According to the GDPR, a controller is “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law”. The primary attribute that sets the controller apart is that they determine the “purposes and means of processing personal data”. The capacity of the controller to decide the purposes and means of processing must be factual.¹⁰⁸ This implies that the controller exercise decision-making power and factual influence over the processing operations.¹⁰⁹ The factual influence can be established by answering questions on “why the processing is happening, who initiated the processing and who benefits from said processing”.¹¹⁰ Pursuant to the GDPR, the controller is obligated to implement technical and organisational measures and ensure that they are able to demonstrate that processing was done in line with the provisions of the regulation.¹¹¹

The GDPR also recognises the concept of a joint controller. The GDPR anticipates scenarios where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing and regards the parties as joint controllers.¹¹² Pursuant to the GDPR, the joint controllers must take transparent steps to determine their respective responsibilities and share the obligation of complying with the requirements imposed by the regulation.¹¹³ This includes but is not limited to the obligations of the joint controllers regarding the exercise of rights of the data subject and their obligation to furnish the data subjects with information from the controller.

¹⁰⁸ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 105.

¹⁰⁹ European Data Protection Supervisor, Guidelines on the concepts of controller, processor and joint controllership under Regulation (EU) 2018/1725, 7 November 2019, 7.

¹¹⁰ *ibid.*

¹¹¹ Article 25(1) and (2) GDPR.

¹¹² Article 26(1) GDPR .

¹¹³ *ibid*; Paul Voigt and Axel von dem Bussche, ‘The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Practical Guide’, (Springer 2017) 18.

Furthermore, the GDPR defines a data processor as any “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller”.¹¹⁴ The controller must ensure that processors acting on their behalf provide sufficient guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure that processing activities comply with the requirements of the GDPR and protect the rights of data subjects.¹¹⁵ The GDPR requires the relationship between the controller and the processor to be governed by a legal instrument such as a contract, union law or member state law.¹¹⁶ However, it should be noted that the processor cannot assign or delegate processing to another processor without the prior written authorisation of the controller.

Recipients refer to “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not. However, public authorities which may receive personal data in the framework of a particular inquiry in accordance with Union or Member State law shall not be regarded as recipients; the processing of those data by those public authorities shall be in compliance with the applicable data protection rules according to the purposes of the processing”. Where personal data is disclosed to recipients, data subjects have a right to receive this information from the controller.¹¹⁷ A concrete analysis of the GDPR roles will be conducted in Deliverable D4.2.

Recommendation 3

It is vital to identify who the controller is with regard to the various processing activities envisaged in CORTEX² in order to ensure that the appropriate party takes responsibility for the obligations imposed on the controller by the GDPR. It is also important to identify the controllers where the responsibility of determining the purposes and means of processing shifts throughout the lifecycle of the project. The role of the parties in the co-development phase of the project as processors or possibly joint controllers must be established in order for the right obligations to apply pursuant to the GDPR. In addition, it must be determined whether their recipients are to be disclosed to data subjects.

¹¹⁴ Article 4(8) GDPR.

¹¹⁵ Article 28(1) GDPR.

¹¹⁶ Article 28(3) GDPR.

¹¹⁷ Article 15(1)(a) GDPR.

3.3.3. Data Protection Principles

All processing activities that fall within the purview of the GDPR must adhere to the principles of the regulation. This implies that the principles of the GDPR are mandatory, and derogation must be provided for by law in pursuit of a legitimate aim and be necessary and proportionate measures in a democratic society.¹¹⁸ Pursuant to the GDPR, the relevant principles are lawfulness, fairness and transparency, purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality, and accountability.¹¹⁹

The fundamentals of these cardinal principles of the GDPR are laid out below:

<p>Lawfulness, fairness and transparency¹²⁰</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The lawfulness of processing personal data requires a legal ground that is stipulated in the GDPR.• The GDPR recognises six lawful grounds for processing personal data. The six legal bases are (1) Consent of the data subject, (2) contractual necessity, (3) Legal obligation of the controller, (4) Vital interest of the data subject or other natural person, (5) performance of a task carried out in the interest of the public (6) legitimate interest of the controller.¹²¹• Data subjects must receive information from the controller in advance about how and why the data is being processed and the risks and consequences of such processing.
<p>Purpose limitation¹²²</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Personal data must be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes.

¹¹⁸ Article 23(1) GDPR; Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 116.

¹¹⁹ Article 5(1) and (2) GDPR.

¹²⁰ Article 5(1)(a) GDPR.

¹²¹ Article 6(1)(a) – (f) GDPR.

¹²² Article 5(1)(b) GDPR.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Further processing of personal data must be compatible with the initial specified, explicit and legitimate purpose.
Data minimisation ¹²³	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Processing of personal data should be limited to what is directly relevant for achieving the declared purpose of the process.
Accuracy ¹²⁴	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The controller must ensure with reasonable certainty that personal data remains correct and up to date.
Storage Limitation ¹²⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The retention of personal data in a form that allows the identification of data subjects should not be longer than necessary.• Retention periods for personal data may be longer where such data is archived strictly for public interest, scientific, statistical or historical purposes, provided the appropriate technical and organisational measures are put in place.• Personal data which has outlived its usefulness should be deleted or anonymised.
Integrity and confidentiality ¹²⁶	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The security of processing activities is crucial, and the controller must ensure that the appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to safeguard personal data from physical and non-physical attacks, including unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage.

¹²³ Article 5(1)(c) GDPR.

¹²⁴ Article 5(1)(d) GDPR.

¹²⁵ Article 5(1)(e) GDPR.

¹²⁶ Article 5(1)(f) GDPR.

Accountability ¹²⁷	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Both the processor and controller have compliance obligations under this principle of the GDPR, and they must be able to demonstrate this compliance to data subjects, the general public and supervisory authorities.
--------------------------------------	--

3.3.4. Data subject rights

The principles of the GDPR discussed in the preceding section do not exist in isolation, and they are reinforced by the rights conferred on data subjects by the regulation. To exercise these rights, the data subject must make a request to the controller or processor invoking these rights, and the controllers are legally obligated to respond to the request. The rights of data subject relevant to CORTEX² are summarised in the table below:

The right to be informed ¹²⁸	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• This right is a by-product of the transparency principle and seeks to arm data subjects with essential information about the controller and the processor. The data subjects will also be informed of the data that is being processed, how the processing operations are conducted and the implication of the processing.
Right of access ¹²⁹	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data subjects are entitled to demand information from the controller about the processing of their personal data.

¹²⁷ Article 5(2) GDPR.

¹²⁸ Article 13 and 14 GDPR.

¹²⁹ Article 15 GDPR.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The information must be delivered in an understandable and intelligible manner.
Right to rectification ¹³⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data subjects should be able to amend incomplete and inaccurate personal data with immediate effect.
Right to erasure (the right to be forgotten) ¹³¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• This right is not absolute but can be exercised in a predefined number of cases, such as where personal data is no longer required or where consent has been withdrawn, or unlawful processing has taken place.• The right can be exercised, provided that implementation costs are reasonable and technical limitations do not inhibit erasure.
The right to restrict processing ¹³²	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data subjects can initiate a temporary restriction on the processing of their personal data for a limited number of scenarios, such as when the accuracy of their data is called into question, the processing is unlawful, or in order to defend a legal claim.
The right to object ¹³³	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data subjects can invoke this right depending on their personal circumstances; however, the exercise of this right must be on one of the grounds recognised by the GDPR, such as to object to direct marketing, automated process, or archiving.

¹³⁰ Article 16 GDPR.

¹³¹ Article 7 GDPR.

¹³² Article 18 GDPR.

¹³³ Article 21 GDPR.

The right to withdraw consent ¹³⁴	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data subjects reserve the right to withdraw consent at any time without negative consequences.
The right to data portability ¹³⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data subjects should be able to exercise their right to receive and share personal data in a structured and easily accessible (machine-readable) format without let or hindrance.
The right to object to automated individual decision making ¹³⁶	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This right is a self-fulfilling general prohibition and does not need to be invoked.
The right to lodge complaints with a supervisory ¹³⁷	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data subject should be able to lodge complaints where they live, work or where their rights have been violated.

3.4. Special categories of personal data

Personal data capable of revealing a data subject's ethnicity, political or religious inclinations, trade union membership, genetic data, health, biometric data or sexual preferences enjoy special protection under the GDPR.¹³⁸ As noted in the previous deliverable D5.1, XR devices collect a range of personal data, especially data that can be used to infer a data subject's mental or emotional state, sexual preferences or physical health condition.¹³⁹

Recommendation 4	Additional attention should be paid to processing operations that involve special categories of personal data throughout the lifecycle of the project to ensure compliance with the GDPR.
-------------------------	---

¹³⁴ Article 7(3) GDPR.

¹³⁵ Article 20 GDPR.

¹³⁶ Article 22 GDPR.

¹³⁷ Article 77 GDPR.

¹³⁸ Article 9 GDPR ; Article 4(13)-(15) GDPR.

¹³⁹ See Deliverable D5.1, CORTEX² requirements and deployment architecture pp. 57-58; Melvin Abraham and others, 'Implications of XR on Privacy, Security and Behaviour: Insights from Experts', Nordic Human-Computer Interaction Conference (Association for Computing Machinery 2022).

3.5. Additional requirements of the GDPR

Besides the GDPR roles of data protection parties, principles of data protection and rights of data subjects highlighted in the preceding sections, there are other requirements of the GDPR that are of profound importance to the design and development of CORTEX². The additional GDPR requirements worth considering are data protection impact assessment (DPIA), data protection by design and default, the role of the data protection officer (DPO) and the recording of processing activities.

Data Protection Impact Assessment is an important requirement of the GDPR. Pursuant to Article 35(1) of the GDPR, data controllers are mandated to conduct an assessment in situations where the use of new technologies can result in a high risk to the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons. The controller must consider the nature, scope, context and purpose of the processing operations to determine whether a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) is required.

Although the GDPR provides some insight into what some of the risks that may necessitate a DPIA, particularly, “physical, material or non-material damage, in particular: where the processing may give rise to discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, damage to the reputation, loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, or any other significant economic or social disadvantage; where data subjects might be deprived of their rights and freedoms or prevented from exercising control over their personal data; where personal data are processed which reveal racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religion or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, data concerning health or data concerning sex life or criminal convictions and offences or related security measures; where personal aspects are evaluated, in particular analysing or predicting aspects concerning performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements, in order to create or use personal profiles; where personal data of

vulnerable natural persons, in particular of children, are processed; or where processing involves a large amount of personal data and affects a large number of data subjects.”¹⁴⁰

In addition, Article 35(3) stipulates some specific cases that require a DPIA: (1) systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons based on automated processing, including profiling, that produces legal or other significant effects (2) processing on a large scale of special categories of data or personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences (3) systemic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale.

Depending on the use cases developed in the CORTEX² pilots and with the amount and categories of data being processed in CORTEX², some of the use cases may involve one or more of the scenarios described in Article 35(3) and embody one or more of the risks discussed in Recital 75 of the GDPR. As such, it is pertinent for the processing activities envisaged with this type of technology to be subject to a DPIA in order to identify and address the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, especially where such processing could compromise professional secrecy, reveal racial or ethnic origin, political beliefs, trade union membership, health data, data relating to sexual preferences or where personal aspects are evaluated, such as performance at work, economic situation, physical or mental health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, and location.

Data protection by design and by default is explicitly provided for in Article 25 of the GDPR. Given the fast pace and increasing capabilities of technological advancements to process personal data, it is pertinent to incorporate data protection principles from the conceptualisation and design phase of such technological development. Data protection by design under EU law requires data controllers to implement measures to facilitate the incorporation of data protection principles and safeguards for the rights of data subjects both at the time of processing and when deciding the means for processing.¹⁴¹ While implementing these measures and safeguards, the controller must give due consideration to the state of the art, the costs of implementation, the nature, scope and purposes of personal data processing

¹⁴⁰ Recital 75 GDPR.

¹⁴¹ C Giakoumopoulos, G Buttarelli, and M O’Flaherty, (n 75) 183.

as well as the severity of the risks to the rights and freedoms of the data subject.¹⁴² A similar requirement is also contained in the Modernised Convention 108.¹⁴³ Under this convention, data controllers and processors must design data processing operations in a manner that prevents or reduces the risk of interference with the rights and freedoms of data subjects while ensuring that they also implement technical and organisational measures that account for the right to data protection at all stages of the processing operations.¹⁴⁴ In the case of CORTEX², it is pertinent to account for the data protection principles and the appropriate technical and organisational safeguards at the nascent stages of the technology.

Data protection by default is provided for in Article 25(2) GDPR and requires the data controller to take appropriate steps to ensure that only personal data that is strictly necessary will be processed by default.¹⁴⁵ Data protection by default also extends to the amount of data collected, the retention period of the data, accessibility and the extent or level of the processing. In the context of CORTEX², it is important to consider innovative privacy-enhancing measures from the onset of the project, such as aggregation techniques, pseudonymization, encryption and authentication techniques.¹⁴⁶

The role of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) in processing activities is provided for in the GDPR.¹⁴⁷ DPOs are responsible for ensuring that the accountability principle is respected, and they advise on and support compliance with data protection rules in organisations that are involved in the processing of personal data.¹⁴⁸ The appointment of a DPO by the data controller and processor is not discretionary, but the obligation to appoint a DPO can be mandatory under some circumstances. Pursuant to Article 37 of the GDPR, the data controller and processor are required to appoint a DPO where the processing is carried out by a public authority or where the processing activities require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large

¹⁴² Ibid; See also ENISA (2015), Privacy and Data Protection by Design from policy to engineering, 12 January 2015; Article 29 Working Party (2017), Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), WP 248 rev.01, 4 October 2017.

¹⁴³ Explanatory Report of Modernized Convention 108, para 89; Article 10 (2) and (3) Modernized Convention 108.

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

¹⁴⁵ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O'Flaherty (n 75) 184.

¹⁴⁶ Ibid.

¹⁴⁷ Article 37-39 GDPR.

¹⁴⁸ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O'Flaherty (n 75) 175.

scale or where there is a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9 and personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10.¹⁴⁹ It should also be noted that the GDPR imposes some guarantees to ensure that DPOs can perform their duties independently and without the interference of the controller or processor.¹⁵⁰

Record of processing activities is one of the additional obligations in the GDPR. This measure is to ensure that controllers and their representatives can demonstrate compliance with the GDPR in line with the accountability principle. The relevant supervisory authorities should also have access to this record when required. Pursuant to Article 30(1) GDPR controllers should keep records of a number of important details such as (1) the name and contact details of the controller and, where applicable, the joint controller, the controller's representative and the data protection officer (2) the purposes of the processing (3) a description of the categories of data subjects and of the categories of personal data (4) the categories of recipients to whom the personal data have been or will be disclosed including recipients in third countries or international organisations; (5) where applicable, transfers of personal data to a third country or an international organisation, including the identification of that third country or international organisation; (6) where possible, the envisaged time limits for erasure of the different categories of data; (7) where possible, a general description of the technical and organisational security measures that have been implemented.

Recommendation 5

The processing activities envisaged in CORTEX² involve the processing of special categories of personal data as well as processing activities that can be deemed regular and systematic monitoring, particularly due to its use in the workplace. Hence, the conduct of DPIAs and the appointment of a DPO are relevant for processing operations envisaged in CORTEX². The appointment of a DPO and the conduct of DPIA are not tasks for the entire consortium, rather, based on the pilots, use

¹⁴⁹ Article 37 (1) (a) –(c) GDPR.

¹⁵⁰ Article 38(2) and (3) GDPR.

	<p>cases and conditions for appointing a DPO and conducting DPIAs identified in subsection 3.5 above, each technical partner in the consortium is aware of these requirements of the GDPR, and is prepared for further recommendations that may follow the concrete analysis conducted in task T4.2. Given the number of processing activities and the nature of the processing activities envisaged in the CORTEX², recording processing activities is an important obligation for technical partners to take into consideration.</p>
--	---

3.6. XR data as biometric data

It is important to point out that certain information gathered through virtual reality can be classified as biometric data. For example, studies have shown that a person can be identified by his facial scans or eye tracking.¹⁵¹ However, those would constitute biometric data.

According to the GDPR, biometric data "means personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data".¹⁵² In addition, the processing of biometric data is only subject to the stricter requirements stipulated by Article 9 GDPR if such data is processed. The GDPR imposes a general prohibition on the processing of biometric data. At the same time, Article 9 (2) recognises the exceptions while processing biometric data. That being said, the processing of biometric data is possible if one or more valid legal bases exist, among others, explicit consent, carrying out the obligations and exercising specific rights of the controller or of the data subject in the field of employment and social security and social protection law, national law, vital interests, or the processing is carried out in the course of its legitimate activities.

¹⁵¹ Bhavishyavani Ravi, 'Privacy issues in virtual reality: eye tracking technology', (Bloomberg Law, 2017).

¹⁵² Article 4 (14) GDPR.

3.7. Processing of Biometric data in XR

As noted earlier in this deliverable, XR involves the processing of a range of biometric data. XR devices have advanced sensing capabilities to capture large amounts of data about the environment, human bystanders and the actions, behaviour and physiology of the users of XR technology.¹⁵³ As a consequence, XR poses serious risks to privacy, security and the ability to understand and influence the behaviour of users.¹⁵⁴

As noted in the preceding section 3.6, behavioural data also constitutes biometric data. In the case of bystanders, the use of XR to sense an environment where bystanders lack the capacity to give consent can lead to XR-enabled surveillance, such as where identity is inferred from gait.¹⁵⁵ XR technology can also collect real-world biometric information like eye or head movements, physical characteristics, residence details, heart rate, and inferred emotions and exposing these sensitive data can put the users at risk, such as where data about living space is used to create an individual's psychological profile.¹⁵⁶

In addition, processing biometric data in XR creates concerns about the invasion of the mental privacy of users of the technology. For instance, research shows that the data collected by AR headsets can unleash the ability to develop a sophisticated, longitudinal understanding of users and bystanders from their behaviour, intentions and actions to their cognitive processes, interests and personality traits.¹⁵⁷ The processing of biometric data such as eye movement (gaze), gait and facial expressions can reveal significant details of a subject's life, including their physical or emotional state.¹⁵⁸ The appropriate technical and organisational measures will be

¹⁵³ Melvin Abraham and others, 'Implications of XR on Privacy, Security and Behaviour: Insights from Experts', Nordic Human-Computer Interaction Conference (ACM 2022) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3546155.3546691>> accessed 4 June 2023.

¹⁵⁴ *ibid.*

¹⁵⁵ Joseph O'Hagan and others, 'Privacy-Enhancing Technology and Everyday Augmented Reality: Understanding Bystanders' Varying Needs for Awareness and Consent' (2023) 6 Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies 177:1.

¹⁵⁶ Chamara Sandeepa, Shen Wang, and Madhusanka Liyanage, 'Privacy of the Metaverse: Current Issues, AI Attacks, and Possible Solutions' (2023).

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369331696_Privacy_of_the_Metaverse_Current_Issues_AI_Attacks_and_Possible_Solutions> accessed 4 June 2023.

¹⁵⁷ *ibid.*

¹⁵⁸ Yuntao Wang and others, 'A Survey on Metaverse: Fundamentals, Security, and Privacy' (2022) PP IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials 1.

required to ensure that this data is not misused or abused. The processing of this type of data is within the purview of the GDPR, and this will be the basis of recommendations that will be proposed to address the risks posed by XR with regard to the biometric data of data subjects.

Moreso, the processing of biometric data in XR can be used to expose health or health-related inferences about users and bystanders who might have certain illnesses or physical injuries that can be detected by analysing the changes in their physical activity, movements or physical patterns.¹⁵⁹ This type of risk is relevant in the context of CORTEX² given that this type of sensitive data can be used to detect users with concentration issues and diagnose users with ADHD in the workplace or used by employers to contest work-related personal injury claims, thereby creating egregious privacy and data protection issues.¹⁶⁰

CORTEX² also includes a speech recognition component that can carry out automatic summarisation of meetings.¹⁶¹ Although the processing of voice data in CORTEX² is not specifically for identification or authentication, the processing of this type of biometric data still raises privacy and data protection issues because voice data is personal data, and can simultaneously be biometric data linkable to a unique individual.¹⁶² In addition, voice data can to a high degree be used to make inferences about an individual's health, gender, weight, height or ethnic and racial background.¹⁶³ Voice data constitute a special category of personal data and is subject to stricter requirements under the GDPR.¹⁶⁴ Speech can also contain sensitive data depending on what is disclosed in such speech, for instance in the context of healthcare

¹⁵⁹ Suchismita Pahi and Calli Schroeder, 'Extended Privacy for Extended Reality: XR Technology Has 99 Problems and Privacy Is Several of Them' (28 August 2022) <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=4202913>> accessed 9 June 2023.

¹⁶⁰ *ibid.*

¹⁶¹ CORTEX², 'Project' <<https://cortex2.eu/project/>> accessed 5 June 2023.

¹⁶² Article 4(1), and (14) GDPR; V. Venkatesan and K. Sentharamaikannan, 'A Comprehensive Survey on Various Biometric Systems' (2018) <<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-Comprehensive-Survey-on-Various-Biometric-Systems-Venkatesan-Sentharamaikannan/0f9c34cb98a6a400954fd9b1d66a712bba86cc81>> accessed 2 August 2023; Shaymaa Adnan Abdulrahman and Bilal Alhayani, 'A Comprehensive Survey on the Biometric Systems Based on Physiological and Behavioural Characteristics' (2023) 80 *Materials Today: Proceedings* 2642; European Data Protection Board (EDPB), 'Guidelines 02/2021 on virtual voice assistants', version 2.0, adopted on 7 July 2021.

¹⁶³ Laurence Minsky and others, *Voice Marketing: Harnessing the Power of Conversational AI to Drive Customer Engagement* (Rowman & Littlefield 2023).

¹⁶⁴ Article 9 GDPR.

or professional secrecy. Hence, recommendations regarding the processing of biometric/sensitive data in CORTEX² will be made in deliverable D4.2 after a thorough analysis of the relevant privacy and data protection framework and the components and architecture of CORTEX² such as the addition of voice processing modules by third parties.

Recommendation 6	This distinction between the data types is important since biometric data is considered sensitive data, and the processing of such data is more strictly regulated by the GDPR. Therefore, it is important to consider the potential implications of processing biometric data in CORTEX ² . As privacy and ethics are essential requirements in CORTEX ² technology, it is crucial to protect any data that is collected and ensure data is used responsibly and in accordance with the requirements of the GDPR.
-------------------------	--

4. The Cybersecurity Framework

XR technology leads to new methods of engaging with digital content in both the real and virtual worlds.¹⁶⁵ However, it does not mean that this technology is not targeted when it comes to cyberattacks.¹⁶⁶ Malicious attacks in an XR environment can be dangerous.¹⁶⁷ Threats in the virtual world can also have serious implications for physical infrastructures, personal safety and human society.¹⁶⁸ Therefore, ensuring cybersecurity in the XR environment is a necessity. Having a cyber security framework is also important given the use of connected devices in

¹⁶⁵ J. Guan, A. Morris, and J. Irizawa, 'Cross-Reality for Extending the Metaverse: Designing Hyper-Connected Immersive Environments with XRI', 2023 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW) (IEEE Computer Society 2023)

<https://doi.ieeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/VRW58643.2023.00071> accessed 5 June 2023..

¹⁶⁶ Kavya Pearlman, 'Virtual Reality Brings Real Risks: Are We Ready?' (USENIX Association 2020) <<https://www.usenix.org/conference/enigma2020/presentation/pearlman>> accessed 5 June 2023.

¹⁶⁷ Laurence Morvan, Francis Hintermann and Armen Ovanessoff, 'Preparing for the Risky World of Extended Reality' [2019] MIT Sloan Management Review <<https://sloanreview.mit.edu/article/preparing-for-the-risky-world-of-extended-reality/>> accessed 5 June 2023.

¹⁶⁸ Wang and others (n 158).

CORTEX², especially for industrial training and production pilots. The use of avatars that replicate the likeness of the users in the workplace creates cybersecurity concerns about access and identity management in XR.

When it comes to the EU laws establishing requirements for cybersecurity, they include the Cybersecurity Act (CSA) and the Network and Information Systems Directive (NIS2). The EU Cybersecurity impending legal frameworks and their relevance to CORTEX² are discussed in this deliverable especially the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA).

4.1. The Cybersecurity Act

The Cybersecurity Act (CSA),¹⁶⁹ which entered into force on 27 June 2019, is the EU's regulation that bears testament to the efforts to strengthen the cybersecurity framework in the EU against the ever-increasing cyber security challenges. The CSA is directly applicable in EU member states and has two main aims (1) to grant the EU Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA) a permanent mandate on the tasks, objectives and organisational matters of ENISA (2) the establishment of European cybersecurity certification schemes in order to guarantee an adequate level of cybersecurity for ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes in the Union.

The CSA intends to achieve a high level of cybersecurity, cyber resilience and trust within the Union. Pursuant to Article 2(13) of the CSA, ICT service “means a service consisting fully or mainly in the transmission, storing, retrieving or processing of information by means of network and information systems”. The processing activities in CORTEX² are consistent with the definition of ICT services envisaged under the definition of ICT services in the CSA. Hence, serious attention should be given to the requirements of the CSA in the course of developing CORTEX².

¹⁶⁹ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (“Cybersecurity Act”), OJ L 151/15, 7.6.2019.

4.1.1. The Role of ENISA

Pursuant to the CSA, ENISA has a number of important roles to play in the overall level of cybersecurity in the EU. These roles emanate from the mandate of the agency to implement its designated tasks under the CSA for the purpose of achieving a high level of cybersecurity across the Union, including those briefly described below:

1. Development and implementation of Union policy and law in the field of cybersecurity and on sector-specific policy and law initiatives. ENISA plays a crucial role in supporting member states in implementing Union policy and law, especially the NIS2 Directive by generating opinions, guidelines, advice and best practices on a range of topical issues such as incident reporting, information sharing and risk management.¹⁷⁰
2. Pursuant to Article 6 CSA, ENISA is tasked with capacity building by rendering assistance to member states in their efforts to improve the detection analysis of cyber threats and also to improve their response to cyberthreat.
3. ENISA's role also includes supporting operational cooperation between Member States, Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies, and between stakeholders in matters of common concern relating to cybercrime and the protection of privacy and personal data.¹⁷¹
4. ENISA has a significant role to play in the internal market regarding cybersecurity certification and standardisation, particularly the development and implementation of union policy on cybersecurity certification of ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes.¹⁷²
5. ENISA is saddled with the responsibility of analysing emerging technologies and providing topic-specific assessments on the anticipated societal, legal, economic and regulatory impact of technological innovations on cybersecurity¹⁷³
6. ENISA also has a responsibility to create public awareness about cybersecurity risks and provide guidance on good practices for individual users, organisations and businesses,

¹⁷⁰ Article 5(2) CSA.

¹⁷¹ Article 7 CSA.

¹⁷² Article 8 CSA.

¹⁷³ Article 9 CSA.

such as cyber-hygiene and cyber-literacy, as well as collaborating with member states to promote cybersecurity education.

7. ENISA also plays a role in research and innovation and international cooperation in the context of cybersecurity.¹⁷⁴

4.1.2. Cybersecurity Certification Framework

Pursuant to Article 46 of the CSA, the European cyber security certification framework shall be established in a bid to improve the conditions for the functioning of the internal market by raising the level of cybersecurity within the internal market. The certification framework is also geared towards fostering a harmonised cybersecurity certification scheme at the EU -Level in order to create a digital single market for ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes.¹⁷⁵ It should be noted that this European cybersecurity certification framework is also required to include a mechanism to establish European cybersecurity certification schemes, as well as mechanisms to ascertain whether ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes have been assessed in accordance with the certification schemes meet the security specifications for protecting the “availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored or transmitted or processed data or functions or services offered by, or accessible via, those products, services and processes throughout their life cycle”.¹⁷⁶

The European Commission is required to publish a Union rolling work programme that identifies strategic priorities for future European cybersecurity certification schemes.¹⁷⁷ It is pertinent to mention that specific ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes are to be included in the work programme on the grounds of market demand and trends in the cyber threat landscape.¹⁷⁸ ENISA has recognised the growing demand for XR and the increasing threat to XR technologies, but a work programme is still pending in this regard.¹⁷⁹ Pursuant to Article

¹⁷⁴ Article 11 and 12 CSA.

¹⁷⁵ Article 46(1) CSA.

¹⁷⁶ Article 46(2) CSA.

¹⁷⁷ Article 47(1) CSA.

¹⁷⁸ Article 47(3) CSA.

¹⁷⁹ ENISA, Cybersecurity Market Analysis Framework V2.0, March 2023; ENISA, Identifying Emerging Cyber Security Threats And Challenges for 2030, (March 2023) <<https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-foresight-cybersecurity-threats-for-2030/@@download/fullReport>> accessed 5 June 2023.

51 CSA, the European cybersecurity certification must designed to meet some specific security objectives. For clarity, the provisions of the CSA are reproduced below. As set out by CSA Article 51, the European cybersecurity certification scheme needs to achieve at least the following security objectives:

1. To protect stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data against accidental or unauthorised storage, processing, access or disclosure during the entire life cycle of the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process.
2. To protect stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data against accidental or unauthorised destruction, loss or alteration or lack of availability during the entire life cycle of the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process.
3. That authorised persons, programs or machines are able only to access the data, services or functions to which their access rights refer.
4. To identify and document known dependencies and vulnerabilities.
5. To record which data, services or functions have been accessed, used or otherwise processed, at what times and by whom.
6. To make it possible to check which data, services or functions have been accessed, used or otherwise processed, at what times and by whom.
7. To verify that ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes do not contain known vulnerabilities.
8. To restore the availability and access to data, services and functions in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident.
9. That ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes are secure by default and by design.
10. That ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes are provided with up-to-date software and hardware that do not contain publicly known vulnerabilities and are provided with mechanisms for secure updates.

In addition, the CSA creates what it calls assurance levels for the European cybersecurity certification scheme and they are categorized into “basic”, “substantial” and “high” assurance levels, depending on the probability and impact of the risk associated with the intended use of

the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process.¹⁸⁰ Where the European cybersecurity certificate or a statement of conformity is issued for ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes with a “basic” assurance level, the evaluation of such product, service or process must include technical documentation.¹⁸¹ In the case of ICT products, services and processes that reach the substantial assurance level, the evaluation must include “a review to demonstrate the absence of publicly known vulnerabilities and testing to demonstrate that the ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes correctly implement the necessary security functionalities.”¹⁸² Where the ICT products, services or process reach the “high” assurance level, at least one of these must be conducted (1) a review to demonstrate the absence of publicly known vulnerabilities; (2) testing to demonstrate that the ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes correctly implement the necessary security functionalities at the state of the art; (3) an assessment of their resistance to skilled attackers, using penetration testing.¹⁸³ Pursuant to Article 53(1) CSA, manufacturers or providers of ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes that only amount to a basic risk assurance level can conduct conformity self-assessment.

Another interesting provision in the CSA is the right to lodge a complaint provided in Article 63 CSA. Natural and legal persons have the right to lodge a complaint with the issuer of a European cybersecurity certificate or with other relevant national cybersecurity certification authorities. Natural and legal persons also have a right to seek judicial remedy in respect of the decisions taken by the authorities or administrative bodies handling complaints under Article 63 CSA.¹⁸⁴ Judicial remedy can also be sought where there is a failure to act on a complaint lodged with the relevant Authorities pursuant to Article 63(1) CSA.¹⁸⁵

Recommendation 7	Given the complexity and interconnectedness of CORTEX ² , it is pertinent to anticipate and determine the risk level of CORTEX ² in light of the provisions of the CSA.
-------------------------	---

¹⁸⁰ Article 52 CSA.

¹⁸¹ Article 52(5) CSA.

¹⁸² Article 52(6) CSA.

¹⁸³ Article 52(7) CSA.

¹⁸⁴ Article 64(1)(a) CSA.

¹⁸⁵ Article 64(1)(b) CSA.

4.2. The NIS 2 Directive

Given the rising sophistication of cyber threats in the EU, the need for an EU-wide, comprehensive and future-proof legal framework with ample coverage of various sectors and services has become a necessity. In order to meet this objective and achieve a uniform and coherent cybersecurity framework in the EU, the NIS Directive was repealed, and the NIS2 directive was adopted in December 2022. Pursuant to NIS2 Directive, member states no longer have wide discretion to determine and designate essential services at the national level. Article 2 of the NIS2 Directive provides that critical entities will now be determined by different factors, including size cap, turnover and activity in predefined sectors contained in the Directive.¹⁸⁶ The NIS2 Directive has also introduced “essential entities” and “important entities” to replace the “essential services” in the repealed Directive.¹⁸⁷

The NIS2 Directive still maintains the minimum harmonization requirement as contained in the repealed directive.¹⁸⁸ This implies that member states can adopt or maintain higher protective measures that are contained in the directive provided such measures are consistent with Union law to which the member state is bound.

However, the NIS directive now requires the relevant entities to adopt the “all-hazards-approach” to secure network and information systems and the physical spaces such systems occupy from physical and non-physical harms like “theft, fire, flood, telecommunication or power failures, or unauthorised physical access and damage to, and interference with, an essential or important entity’s information and information processing facilities, which could compromise the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored, transmitted or processed data or of the services offered by, or accessible via, network and information systems”.¹⁸⁹

Before pointing out the obligations of the essential/ important entities, it is important to note that pursuant to the NIS2 Directive, the following sectors have been identified as critical sectors,

¹⁸⁶ Annex I NIS2 Directive.

¹⁸⁷ Article 3 NIS2 Directive.

¹⁸⁸ Article 5 NIS2 Directive.

¹⁸⁹ Recital 79 NIS2 Directive.

energy, transport, banking, financial market infrastructures, drinking water, wastewater, digital infrastructure, ICT service management (business-to-business), public administration, space and health.¹⁹⁰ In addition, Annex II of the NIS2 Directive also identifies additional sectors that are subject to the provisions of the directive, such as postal and courier services, waste management, manufacture, production and distribution of chemicals, production, processing and distribution of food, digital providers, research, manufacturing.

In order to be compliant with the provisions of the NIS2 directive, the Essential entities identified in the NIS2 Directive must adhere to the obligations imposed by the directive regarding implementing “appropriate and proportionate technical, operational and organisational measures for managing the risks posed to the security of network and information systems used for their operations or for providing their services”.¹⁹¹ The measures to be implemented must take into account the state of the art in terms of cyber security, the cost of implementation, and any other relevant European and International standards for managing security risks to network and information systems.¹⁹²

In line with this obligation Article 21(2) NIS2 Directive provides that these entities must comply with a minimum level of security including: “(1) policies on risk analysis and information system security; (2) incident handling; (3) business continuity, such as backup management and disaster recovery, and crisis management; (4) supply chain security, including security-related aspects concerning the relationships between each entity and its direct suppliers or service providers; (5) security in network and information systems acquisition, development and maintenance, including vulnerability handling and disclosure; (6) policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures; (7) basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training; (8) policies and procedures regarding the use of cryptography and, where appropriate, encryption; (9) human resources security, access control policies and asset management; (10) the use of multi-factor authentication or continuous

¹⁹⁰ Annex I NIS2 Directive.

¹⁹¹ Article 21(1) NIS2 Directive.

¹⁹² *ibid.*

authentication solutions, secured voice, video and text communications and secured emergency communication systems within the entity, where appropriate.”

The NIS2 Directive also imposes reporting obligations on essential and important entities pursuant to Article 23 NIS2 Directive. This provision requires member states to mandate essential and important to notify the competent authority or responsible national bodies of any incidents that have a significant impact on service delivery without any undue delay. Under the repealed Directive, what constituted a “significant incident” was always a contentious issue. However, this has been resolved in the NIS2 Directive. Article 6(6) NIS2 Directive defines an incident as “an event compromising the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored, transmitted or processed data or of the services offered by, or accessible via, network and information system”¹⁹³ An incident is deemed significant under the NIS2 Directive: (1) if it has caused or is capable of causing severe operational disruption of services or financial loss for the essential or important entity (2) when it has affected or is capable of affecting other natural or legal persons by causing considerable material or non-material damage.¹⁹⁴ It should be noted that for the purpose of meeting the notification obligations the entities concerned shall without undue delay, and where applicable submit

1. an early warning of any event, within 24 hours of becoming aware of the significant incident. The early warning must indicate whether the suspected cause of the significant incident was unlawful or malicious acts or whether there could be a cross-border impact.
2. an incident notification of any event, within 72 hours of becoming aware of the significant incident. The incident notification shall update the information provided in the early warning and include an initial assessment that indicates the severity and impact of the incident and any indicators of compromise.
3. An intermediate report on relevant status updates upon request of a competent authority
4. A final report not later than one month after turning in the incident notification. The final report should include, (i) a detailed description of the incident, including its severity and

¹⁹³ Article 6(6) NIS2 Directive.

¹⁹⁴ Article 23(3) NIS2 Directive.

impact; (ii) the type of threat or root cause that is likely to have triggered the incident; (iii) applied and ongoing mitigation measures; (iv) where applicable, the cross-border impact of the incident;

Recommendation 8

Based on the projected use cases of CORTEX², it is already possible to make a preliminary identification of some of the relevant sectors and subsectors for CORTEX² and this will form the starting point for the more concrete analysis of the cybersecurity requirements of CORTEX². For instance, under the digital infrastructure sector, providers of publicly available electronic communications services are one of the relevant subsectors. In addition, CORTEX² is intended for use in production (manufacturing) and can also be used in a number of business cases, including banking, public administration and any other sector that adopts XR remote-working or teleconferencing technology.

4.3. Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)

As a result of the rise in smart and connected products, a cybersecurity incident in one product can start a chain of events, potentially disrupting social and economic activities across the internal market.¹⁹⁵ It is against this backdrop that the EU Commission introduced the ‘Cyber Resilience Act’ (CRA) on 15 September 2022, to ensure a coherent cybersecurity framework with mandatory requirements for manufacturers of products with digital elements, in a bid to solidify the EU’s 2020 Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade,¹⁹⁶ as well as the Council

¹⁹⁵ Briefing of EPRS | European Parliamentary Research Service, EU Cyber-resilience Act; [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/739259/EPRS_BRI\(2022\)739259_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/739259/EPRS_BRI(2022)739259_EN.pdf)

¹⁹⁶ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final.

Conclusions of 2 December 2020¹⁹⁷ and the Resolution of the European Parliament of 10 June 2021.¹⁹⁸

Article 114 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) has been recognised as the legal basis of the CRA, as it provides for the adoption of measures to ensure the establishment and functioning of the internal market.¹⁹⁹ Hence, in this section of the deliverable, we consider the scope of the CRA, the requirements for placing products with digital elements on the market and the various obligations imposed on economic operators by the CRA. The various conformity assessment rules and the market enforcement mechanisms will be slightly touched up in order to highlight some important requirements for CORTEX².

Pursuant to Article 2(1) CRA, the focus of the CRA is on products with digital elements whose intended or reasonably foreseeable use includes a direct or indirect logical or physical connection to a device or network. Products with digital elements refer to “any software or hardware product and its remote data processing solutions, including software or hardware components to be placed on the market separately”. Thus, the CRA proposal has a broad application which includes software as a separate product from the hardware and this can be gleaned from Recital 44 of the CRA.²⁰⁰ It is pertinent to establish the scope of the CRA proposal given the nature of the products in CORTEX² and the requirements that will likely extend to XR products in the long run.

Another important highlight of the CRA proposal is that it provides an elaborate framework for placing products with digital elements on the market, especially the essential security requirements and vulnerability handling requirements for such products.²⁰¹ These requirements are contained in Annex I of the CRA proposal and state that:

¹⁹⁷ Proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148, COM(2020) 823 final.

¹⁹⁸ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act); Pier Giorgio Chiara, ‘The Cyber Resilience Act: The EU Commission’s Proposal for a Horizontal Regulation on Cybersecurity for Products with Digital Elements’ (2022) 3 International Cybersecurity Law Review 255.

¹⁹⁹ Chiara (n 130).

²⁰⁰ *ibid* 258.

²⁰¹ Article 5 CRA.

1. Products with digital elements shall be designed, developed and produced in such a way that they ensure an appropriate level of cybersecurity based on the risks;
2. Products with digital elements shall be delivered without any known exploitable vulnerabilities;
3. On the basis of the risk assessment referred to in Article 10(2) and where applicable, products with digital elements shall:
 - a. Be delivered with a secure by default configuration, including the possibility to reset the product to its original state.
 - b. Ensure protection from unauthorised access by appropriate control mechanisms, including but not limited to authentication, identity or access management systems.
 - c. Protect the confidentiality of stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data, personal or other, such as by encrypting relevant data at rest or in transit by state-of-the-art mechanisms.
 - d. Protect the integrity of stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data, personal or other, commands, programs and configuration against any manipulation or modification not authorised by the user, as well as report on corruptions.
 - e. Process only data, personal or other, that are adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for relation to the intended use of the product ('minimisation of data).
 - f. Protect the availability of essential functions, including the resilience against and mitigation of denial of service attacks.
 - g. Minimise their own negative impact on the availability of services provided by other devices or networks.
 - h. Be designed, developed and produced to limit attack surfaces, including external interfaces.
 - i. Be designed, developed and produced to reduce the impact of an incident using appropriate exploitation mitigation mechanisms and techniques.
 - j. Provide security-related information by recording and/or monitoring relevant internal activity, including the access to or modification of data, services or functions.

- k. Ensure that vulnerabilities can be addressed through security updates, including, where applicable, through automatic updates and the notification of available updates to users.

The CRA also provides vulnerability handling requirements for manufacturers of products with digital elements.²⁰² Manufacturers must among other things, (1) identify and document vulnerabilities and components contained in the product (2) address and remediate vulnerabilities without delay, including by providing security updates (3) apply effective and regular tests and reviews of the security of the product (4)publically [sic] disclose information about fixed vulnerabilities (5) establish and enforce a policy on coordinated vulnerability disclosure (6) take measures to facilitate the sharing of information about potential vulnerabilities (7) provide for mechanisms to securely distribute updates for products (8) ensure that, where security patches or updates are available to address identified security issues, they are disseminated without delay and free of charge.

Recommendation 9

CORTEX² requires a robust emergency response strategy and personnel with vast experience and capabilities to respond quickly to potential cybersecurity attacks. CORTEX² should have a cybersecurity strategy capable of keeping backup systems and contingency plans to ensure availability and resilience. Therefore, the necessary planning and action to implement this recommendation is required of the technical partners in the CORTEX² project.

5. Requirements from ancillary EU legal framework

This section of the deliverable provides an overview of additional legal frameworks that are relevant to the CORTEX² project with specific reference to digital services and data governance within the EU single market. The section will draw insights from the EU on the relevant policy measures to drive innovation, stimulate the uptake of AI and promote better use of data in line

²⁰² Annex I CRA

with the European Strategy for Data. In line with the foregoing, the relevant legislations that have a bearing on data-driven innovation in the EU such as the Data Governance Act, the Data Act proposal, the Digital Markets Act and the Digital Services Act will be introduced in this section of the deliverable.

5.1. Overview of the European Strategy for Data

The EU Commission has recognised the importance of data in driving the EU's economic and societal endeavours in the coming years however, the commission is equally conscious of the fact this innovation should not be at the expense of European values, fundamental rights and data protection rules.²⁰³ In a bid to become a leading role model for making better business and public sector decisions supported by good quality data that is available for use and re-use.²⁰⁴ To achieve this, the EU Commission has laid out a comprehensive approach to the data economy with the goal of increasing the “use of, and demand for, data and data-enabled products and services throughout the Single Market”. This includes having a common European Union rule around data to ensure data flows within the EU and across various sectors and an open and trustworthy data governance mechanism.

Furthermore, the legislative and policy measures for European data strategy is hinged on four pillars, namely, (1) establishing a cross-sectoral governance framework for data access and use, (2) creating an enabling environment through investments in data and strengthening Europe's capabilities and infrastructures for hosting, processing and using data, as well as interoperability (3) empower individuals on how to enforce their rights regarding the use of the personal data they generate (4) establishing common data spaces in strategic sectors and domains of public interest, including the Common European industrial (manufacturing) data space which has some relevance for the industrial pilot of CORTEX². As noted earlier, CORTEX² includes a pilot phase for industrial remote maintenance and intends to support business cases involving the adoption of XR in manufacturing processes as a possible benefit of CORTEX². The industrial data, such as machine status, breakdowns, service orders, etc, collected in the course

²⁰³ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions A European strategy for data 2020, COM(2020)66.

²⁰⁴ *ibid.*

of remote industrial maintenance and manufacturing can be useful for predictive maintenance or smart manufacturing.²⁰⁵

5.2. EU Data Governance Act

The Data Governance Act came into force on June 23, 2022, and will become applicable from September 2023.²⁰⁶ In line with the European strategy for data, the Data Governance Act is a cross-sectoral instrument that seeks to create an enabling environment for the safe re-use of public sector data and foster data collection for the common good.²⁰⁷ This legislation is particularly relevant because it defines how public sector bodies can access data held by private bodies in a manner that preserves privacy and confidentiality. Pursuant to Article 14 of the Data Act a data holder shall upon the request of a public sector body or a Union institution agency or body furnish such public sector body with the requested data. This request has to be based on exigent circumstances or exceptional needs such as public emergencies like public health emergencies, natural disasters and major cyber security incidents. CORTEX² includes use cases in Crisis management, hence the relevance of this legal framework.

The Data Act itself defines a public emergency as “an exceptional situation negatively affecting the population of the Union, a Member State or part of it, with a risk of serious and lasting repercussions on living conditions or economic stability, or the substantial degradation of economic assets in the Union or the relevant Member State(s);” This definition can accommodate a variety of reasons for access to privately held data, provided there are serious risks and severe economic repercussions.

²⁰⁵ ‘Manufacturing Data Spaces - Predictive Maintenance | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future’ (29 July 2020) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/events/manufacturing-data-spaces-predictive-maintenance>> accessed 30 May 2023; ‘Data Spaces for Manufacturing - Current State of Play | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future’ (23 November 2020) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/events/data-spaces-manufacturing-current-state-play>> accessed 30 May 2023.

²⁰⁶ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 OJ L 152 (Data Governance Act).

²⁰⁷ Impact Assessment Report on European Data Governance Act, ‘Data Governance Act Explained | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future’ <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-governance-act-explained>> accessed 16 June 2023.

Given the cross-sectoral nature of the pilots and various use cases envisaged in the project, it is pertinent to consider how CORTEX² would be designed and developed in a manner that stimulates data exchange and strengthens data-sharing mechanisms across the EU.²⁰⁸

Recommendation 10	The CORTEX ² project should anticipate and prepare for the possible re-use of data amassed in the course of the project and establish mechanisms that will ensure compliance with the DGA if a request is made by a public authority.
--------------------------	--

5.3. The EU Data Act

The Data Act proposal is a step in harmonising the rules on fair access to and (re)use of data in furtherance of the European Strategy for data.²⁰⁹ This Data Act proposal intends to ensure fairness in the EU digital environment with regard to who can access and use data generated across all economic sectors in the EU to create value, including data generated by IoT devices.²¹⁰ This impending legislation also seeks to give users of connected/IoT devices and virtual assistants access to the data generated by them and this is particularly relevant in the context of data generated by users of XR products and services envisaged in CORTEX².²¹¹ For instance, the availability of data about the functioning of industrial equipment will allow factories to

²⁰⁸ Inge Graef and Raphael Gellert, 'The European Commission's Proposed Data Governance Act: Some Initial Reflections on the Increasingly Complex EU Regulatory Puzzle of Stimulating Data Sharing' [2021] SSRN Electronic Journal <<https://www.ssrn.com/abstract=3814721>> accessed 22 May 2023.

²⁰⁹ 'A European Strategy for Data | Shaping Europe's Digital Future' (16 May 2023) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>> accessed 4 June 2023; Alexandru Circiumaru and others, 'How to Improve Smart Contracts in the European Union Data Act' (2023) 2 Digital Society 9.

²¹⁰ Alexandru Circiumaru and others, 'How to Improve Smart Contracts in the European Union Data Act' (2023) 2 Digital Society 9; Wolfgang Kerber, 'Governance of IoT Data: Why the EU Data Act Will Not Fulfill Its Objectives' (2023) 72 GRUR International 120.

²¹¹ Recital 22 Data Act.

optimise operational cycles improve production lines and enhance supply chain management through data-driven techniques like machine learning.²¹²

Pursuant to Article 2(4) of the Data Act proposal, “virtual assistants’ means software that can process demands, tasks or questions including based on audio, written input, gestures or motions, and based on those demands, tasks or questions provides access their own and third-party services or control their own and third-party devices”. The CORTEX² project involves the development of a virtual assistant that can respond to audio, text and gesture-based instructions. Given the fact that the provisions of the Data Act proposal apply to data generated by virtual assistants, it is pertinent to consider the provisions of the Data Act proposal in the development of CORTEX².²¹³

It is pertinent to note that the Data Act also amplifies the right to data portability guaranteed under Article 20 of the GDPR and this connection will be explored further in subsequent deliverables.²¹⁴ However, it is important to note that the Data Act proposal is concerned with “the ability for customers of data processing services, including cloud and edge services, to switch from one data processing service to another while maintaining a minimum functionality of service, is a key condition for a more competitive market with lower entry barriers for new service providers”.²¹⁵ The provision of the Data Act proposal is also relevant given that the digital workplace will be localised in the cloud, hence, CORTEX² should take steps to ensure a competitive market with lower entry barriers for new service providers.²¹⁶

5.4. The Digital Services Package

The package is comprised of the Digital Services Act (DSA) and the Digital Market Act (DMA) which are the legislative frameworks by the EU to regulate online digital platforms, such as online markets places, search engines, social media platforms and other information society

²¹² ‘Data Act | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future’ <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-act>> accessed 12 June 2023.

²¹³ Recital 22 Data Act.

²¹⁴ Daniela Bresic, Lalova-Spinks Teodora and others, ‘The Broadening of the Right to Data Portability for IoT Products: Who Does the Act Actually Empower?’ [2022] CiTiP Working Paper Series 27.

²¹⁵ Recital 69 Data Act.

²¹⁶ *ibid.*

services.²¹⁷ The DMA is particularly relevant in the context of remote working given the obligations imposed on intermediary services, “large online platforms” or “gatekeepers”²¹⁸ This legislation aims to provide a comprehensive set of rules to ensure that online platforms are safer, respect the fundamental rights of users and foster growth and competitiveness in the EU with regard to the creation of new innovative services in the internal market.²¹⁹ The DSA's primary focus is harmful and illegal goods, services and content online, while the DMA is concerned with enabling access to the digital market and discouraging a range of prohibited behaviour in the internal market.²²⁰ Both of these legislations will now be highlighted individually.

The Digital Services Act: this piece of legislation is a horizontal initiative that stipulates the harmonised rules for providing intermediary services in the EU internal market. This is an improvement in the liability regimes for information society service providers.²²¹ The DSA is relevant for CORTEX² because, following the expanded definition of intermediary services in Article 2(1) (f) DSA includes online platforms that provide mere conduit services, caching and hosting services. One or more of these services are easily foreseeable in the context of this project, such as hosting and conduit services. The safeguards and due diligence requirements in Chapter 3 of the DSA, such as those regarding transparency obligations, cooperation with competent national authorities, and the notice and action mechanisms, will prove useful in the event of misuse of the technology to create harmful content or engage in illegal or harmful activities in the virtual environment.²²²

On the other hand, the DMA came into force on 1 November 2022 and became applicable on 2 May 2023. The DMA is concerned with unfair business practices and economic imbalances by

²¹⁷ Aída Ponce Del Castillo, ‘The Digital Services Act Package’ <<https://policycommons.net/artifacts/2067215/the-digital-services-act-package/2821429/>> accessed 22 May 2023.

²¹⁸ *ibid.*

²¹⁹ Maria Luisa Chiarella, ‘Digital Markets Act (DMA) and Digital Services Act (DSA): New Rules for the EU Digital Environment’ (2022) 9 Athens Journal of Law 33; Paragraph 3 of the Explanatory Memorandum of the DSA.

²²⁰ *ibid.*

²²¹ *ibid.*

²²² Article 11 – 18 DSA.

gatekeepers and the negative consequence of these concerns on the internal market.²²³ Pursuant to Article 2(1) of the DMA, gatekeeper means an undertaking providing core platform services” like virtual assistants, online social networking services, online intermediation services and video sharing platform services. An undertaking is designated a gatekeeper if it provides a core platform service which is an important gateway for business users to reach end users.²²⁴ These designated gatekeepers must comply with the obligations stipulated in the DMA. With regard to the DMA, CORTEX² promises several “end user” facing benefits, especially facilitating improved interaction during product development in manufacturing processes and improving customer experience. This could be by utilizing one or more of the core platform services like video sharing, online intermediation and virtual assistants as stipulated in Article 2(2) DMA. Pursuant to Article 3(1)(b) DMA, an undertaking shall be designated as a gatekeeper if “it provides a core platform service which is an important gateway for business users to reach end users”. The CORTEX² pilots, and possibly some of the use cases, could meet the criteria for designation as gatekeepers if there is substantial adoption across various sectors. Therefore, it is important to develop the technology in a way that fosters competition. For instance, by making the platform interoperable and ensuring data portability in line with the GDPR so that business users can switch to other services if the need arises.²²⁵

5.5. Labour Law in the European Union

The rise in the use of digital tools to facilitate teleworking has created a range of concerns. According to the Council of Europe, “new communication technologies increase the opportunities available to employers for violating their workers' privacy, making use of full-scale social monitoring in firms, by placing employees under electronic, audio-visual or computerised surveillance (e.g. video surveillance, checking of e-mail or voice box content, monitoring of phone calls, holding of files on employees and data relating to their perceived career profile, personality, potential and state of health, assessment of the work done by employees, as well as their working hours, time spent travelling, and productivity. Surveillance methods include

²²³ Maria Luisa Chiarella, ‘Digital Markets Act (DMA) and Digital Services Act (DSA): New Rules for the EU Digital Environment’ (2022) 9 Athens Journal of Law 33.

²²⁴ Article 3(1)(b) DMA.

²²⁵ Recital 59 DMA.

electronic badges, PAX systems, analysis of telephone calls, and log tracking, etc.”²²⁶ In addition, the EU parliament is concerned about how these technological innovations create new forms of employment that are outside the scope of pre-existing legal frameworks. There are also concerns about the increasingly blurring lines between work and private life and issues relating to the health and safety of workers, especially the early adopters of new and emerging technologies like XR.²²⁷

As mentioned above, employee privacy is a challenge for the use of extended reality in the workplace, especially given the specific rules for data protection in employment relations stipulated in the GDPR and the Council of Europe’s (CoE) Employment Data Recommendation.²²⁸ Under the GDPR, employees have rights as data subjects, including the right to be informed. In addition, in line with this principle of the GDPR, employees have a right to know the retention period for their data. Employees need to be able to exercise their right over personal data, including the avatars generated in the course of employment. CORTEX² should also be concerned with the obligations regarding transparency and consultation with employees in line with the CoE recommendation, with respect to components of the technology that are capable of being used for surveillance in the workplace.²²⁹

Hence, it is pertinent to ensure compliance with the rules and regulations on employment and working conditions at both the EU level and national levels, especially with regard to privacy and data protection. For instance, by ensuring respect for the right to non-discrimination enshrined in Article 21 of the Charter. CORTEX² must provide adequate safeguards to preserve the rights of employees and ensure that the legal obligations of employers under European and EU law are met, specifically stipulations on the rights of employees to be protected from

²²⁶ Social, Health and Family Affairs Committee, ‘Impact of New Technologies on Labour Legislation’ (Council of Europe 2000) Doc. 8751 <<https://assembly.coe.int/nw/xml/XRef/X2H-Xref-ViewHTML.asp?FileID=8948&lang=EN>> accessed 23 May 2023.

²²⁷ ‘Hoe verbetert de EU werknemersrechten en arbeidsomstandigheden? | Nieuws | Europees Parlement’ (14 May 2019) <<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/nl/headlines/society/20190506STO44344/hoer-verbetert-de-eu-werknemersrechten-en-arbeidsomstandigheden>> accessed 22 May 2023.

²²⁸ Giakoumopoulos, Buttarelli, and O’Flaherty (n 75) 330; Recommendation No. R (89) 2 of the Committee of Ministers to Member states on the protection of personal data used for employment purposes.

²²⁹ Council of Europe, Committee of Ministers (2015), Recommendation Rec (2015)5 to member states on the processing of personal data in the context of employment, April 2015.

discrimination and the right to fair and just working conditions.²³⁰ The provision of the EU charter against discrimination is relevant because of the use of employee avatars. The use of avatars raises issues around the physical characteristics of the avatars, where employees select avatars with racial characteristics or decide to omit certain physical attributes. The CORTEX² framework must also be designed and developed in a way that does not exclude persons with impaired physical abilities.²³¹ In addition, the platform should include measures to discourage discrimination in the course of interactions on XR. This is to prevent scenarios where XR users input or perpetrate obscenities or input derogatory content into the virtual environment about race, religion, gender, sexual identity, nationality, or disability or engage in other anti-social behaviours that make the virtual environment less safe and inclusive for other users.²³²

Recommendation 11

CORTEX² should implement technical features to ensure the dignity and safety of users (employees) in the virtual environment. For example, by allowing users to make reasonable customisations to their experiences and moderate their interactions in the virtual environment.

6. Conclusion

CORTEX² is being developed in order to facilitate remote work across a range of use cases. This spells huge benefits for both employees and employers of labour, such as economic and time-saving benefits and improved work processes. However, these benefits are equally matched by

²³⁰ Article 21 and Article 31 the Charter.

²³¹ Muhammad Reza Syariffudin Zaki and Paulus Aluk Fadjar Dwi Santo, 'International Labour Law Perspectives on the Metaverse', proceedings of the 3rd Asia Pacific International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management, Johor Bahru, Malaysia, September 13-15, 2022.

²³² Mangina and Eleni, 'The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Social and Multi-User Spaces in VR: Trolling, Harassment, and Online Safety [2021] The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Social and Multi-User Spaces in VR: Trolling, Harassment, and Online Safety 1.

a plethora of legal and ethical risks that make XR less attractive. In order to mitigate these risks, appropriate measures supported by law and ethical considerations can prove useful. However, before a concrete analysis can be done to ascertain how much the EU legal framework and the relevant ethical principle can contribute to developing a CORTEX² framework that is consistent with the fundamental rights and values of the EU, it is pertinent to first identify the legal framework and ethical guidelines. Hence, this deliverable has gone ahead to introduce the ethical principles and legal frameworks that are worthy of consideration, in addition to 11 preliminary recommendations to guide the initial stages of the project. These recommendations as summarised below and will be updated after task T4.2 has been concluded:

1. High-quality data sets are required for training the AI models in CORTEX², especially the large language models. The training data must be accurate and representative.²³³
2. CORTEX² must consider the safety of users from the design stage by identifying the safety concerns associated with each added component, technical feature or use case in the project.²³⁴
3. Disclosure of the capabilities of the various novel technical modules of the CORTEX² framework is essential for assessing their compliance with privacy and data protection requirements.²³⁵
4. Due to the co-development and collaboration in various components of the CORTEX² framework, further analysis should be conducted to simplify the roles and responsibilities of the various technical parties in line with the GDPR.²³⁶
5. The processing of special categories of personal data requires stricter measures. CORTEX² must specify the special categories of data to be used, including behavioural and biometric data.²³⁷

²³³ See Recommendation 1.

²³⁴ *ibid.*

²³⁵ See Recommendation 2.

²³⁶ See Recommendation 3.

²³⁷ See Recommendation 4 and 6.

6. Conducting a DPIA, appointing a DPO and keeping records of processing activities can help shore up privacy and data protection efforts in the face of the processing activities envisaged in CORTEX².²³⁸
7. Identify possible and known risks and vulnerabilities concerning cybersecurity of the CORTEX² framework, e.g. those arising from hardware or other novel technical components, and mitigations to address them.²³⁹
8. From the onset, CORTEX² should consider interoperability and the possibility of data sharing for the future of the project.²⁴⁰
9. Ensure that in designing and developing the technical features of CORTEX², the users' safety and dignity in the virtual environment are not compromised, users must retain control over their interactions in the virtual environment.²⁴¹

²³⁸ See Recommendation 5.

²³⁹ See Recommendation 7, 8 and 9.

²⁴⁰ See Recommendation 10.

²⁴¹ See Recommendation 11.

Bibliography

Primary Sources

Legislation

Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CETS No. 108, 1981

Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) OJ L 333, 27.12.2022

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act) (Text with EEA relevance) OJ L 151, 7.6.2019

Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (“Cybersecurity Act”), OJ L 151/15, 7.6.2019.

Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act);

Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013, Article 19.

Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act) (Text with EEA relevance); PE/30/2022/REV/1, OJ L 277, 27.10.2022; Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act) (Text with EEA relevance) PE/17/2022/REV/, OJ L 265, 12.10.2022

Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 OJ L 152 (Data Governance Act)

Cases

ECtHR, *S. and Marper v. the United Kingdom* [GC], Nos. 30562/04 and 30566/04, 4 December 2008

CJEU, *Joined cases C-92/09 and C-93/09, Volker und Markus Schecke GbR and Hartmut Eifert v. Land Hessen* [GC], 9 November 2010

CJEU, *Joined cases C-293/12 and C-594/12, Digital Rights Ireland Ltd v. Minister for Communications, Marine and Natural Resources and Others and Kärntner Landesregierung and Others* [GC], 8 April 2014

D4.1 – Legal and Ethical Inventory

Digital Rights Ireland Ltd v. Minister for Communications, Marine and Natural Resources and Others and Kärntner Landesregierung and Others [GC], 8 April 2014

Others

COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A European strategy for data 2020, COM(2020)66

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, The European Council, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions, Artificial Intelligence for Europe (COM 2018) 237

High-Level Expert Group on AI, 'Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI' (2019)

ENISA (2015), Privacy and Data Protection by Design from policy to engineering, 12 January 2015

Article 29 Working Party (2017), Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), WP 248 rev.01, 4 October 2017

Proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148, COM(2020) 823 final.

Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL LAYING DOWN HARMONISED RULES ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT) AND AMENDING CERTAIN UNION LEGISLATIVE ACTS COM/2021/206 final

Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act) COM/2022/68 final

Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on European data governance (Data Governance Act) COM/2020/767 final

Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020

Secondary Sources

Books

C Giakoumopoulos, G Buttarelli, and M O'Flaherty, 'Handbook on European Data Protection Law 2018 Edition' (2018)

Paul Voigt and Axel von dem Bussche, *The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Practical Guide* (Springer 2017)

Articles

Alexandru Circiumaru and others, 'How to Improve Smart Contracts in the European Union Data Act' (2023) 2 Digital Society 9

D4.1 – Legal and Ethical Inventory

- Allan Rosas, 'The Court of Justice of the European Union: A Human Rights Institution?' (2022) 14 Journal of Human Rights Practice 204
- Andreas Madsen, Siva Reddy, and Sarath Chandar, 'Post-Hoc Interpretability for Neural NLP: A Survey' (2022) 55 ACM Computing Surveys 155:1
- Buomsoo Kim, Jinsoo Park, and Jihae Suh, 'Transparency and Accountability in AI Decision Support: Explaining and Visualizing Convolutional Neural Networks for Text Information' (2020) 134 Decision Support Systems 113302
- Chamara Sandeepa, Shen Wang, and Madhusanka Liyanage, 'Privacy of the Metaverse: Current Issues, AI Attacks, and Possible Solutions' (2023).
- Daniela Bresic, Lalova-Spinks Teodora and others, 'The Broadening of the Right to Data Portability for IoT Products: Who Does the Act Actually Empower?' [2022] CiTiP Working Paper Series 27.
- Dirk Hovy and Shrimai Prabhumoye, 'Five Sources of Bias in Natural Language Processing' (2021) 15 Language and Linguistics Compass e12432
- Dylan Fox and Isabel Guenette Thornton, 'The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Extended Reality (XR) Ethics and Diversity, Inclusion, and Accessibility' [2022] The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Extended Reality (XR) Ethics and Diversity, Inclusion, and Accessibility 1
- Gianluigi Riva and Simona Tiribelli, 'Moral and Legal Autonomy in the Era of Artificial Intelligence' (S&F_scienzaefilosofia.it 2022)
- Giovanni Sartor, 'Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights: Between Law and Ethics' (2020) 27 Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law 705.
- Inge Graef and Raphael Gellert, 'The European Commission's Proposed Data Governance Act: Some Initial Reflections on the Increasingly Complex EU Regulatory Puzzle of Stimulating Data Sharing' [2021] SSRN Electronic Journal
- Jie Guan, Alexis Morris, and Jay Irizawa, 'Cross-Reality for Extending the Metaverse: Designing Hyper-Connected Immersive Environments with XRI', 2023 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW) (IEEE Computer Society 2023)
- Joseph O'Hagan and others, 'Privacy-Enhancing Technology and Everyday Augmented Reality: Understanding Bystanders' Varying Needs for Awareness and Consent' (2023) 6 Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies 177:1
- Louis Rosenberg, 'Regulation of the Metaverse: A Roadmap: The Risks and Regulatory Solutions for Largescale Consumer Platforms.', *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Virtual and Augmented Reality Simulations* (Association for Computing Machinery 2022)
- Maria Luisa Chiarella, 'Digital Markets Act (DMA) and Digital Services Act (DSA): New Rules for the EU Digital Environment' (2022) 9 Athens Journal of Law 33
- Mark McGill, 'The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Extended Reality (XR) and the Erosion of Anonymity and Privacy' [2021] Extended Reality (XR) and the Erosion of Anonymity and Privacy - White Paper 1
- Melodena Stephens, 'The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Metaverse and Its Governance' [2022] The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) Report-Metaverse and Its Governance
- Melvin Abraham and others, 'Implications of XR on Privacy, Security and Behaviour: Insights from Experts', Nordic Human-Computer Interaction Conference (Association for Computing Machinery 2022)

D4.1 – Legal and Ethical Inventory

Morvan, L., Hintermann, F., & Ovanessoff, A. (2020). Preparing for the risky world of extended reality. *MIT Sloan management review*, 61(2)

Natali Helberger and Nicholas Diakopoulos, 'ChatGPT and the AI Act' (2023) 12 *Internet Policy Review*

Nikos Th. Nikolinakos, 'Ethical Principles for Trustworthy AI' in Nikos Th. Nikolinakos (ed), *EU Policy and Legal Framework for Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and Related Technologies - The AI Act* (Springer International Publishing 2023)

Oliver Diggelmann and Maria Nicole Cleis, 'How the Right to Privacy Became a Human Right' (2014) 14 *Human Rights Law Review* 441

Pearlman, K., & Initiative, X. S. (2020). Virtual reality brings real risks: Are we ready. *USENIX Association: Berkeley, CA, USA*

Pier Giorgio Chiara, 'The Cyber Resilience Act: The EU Commission's Proposal for a Horizontal Regulation on Cybersecurity for Products with Digital Elements' (2022) 3 *International Cybersecurity Law Review* 255

Praveen Kumar Reddy Maddikunta and others, 'Industry 5.0: A Survey on Enabling Technologies and Potential Applications' (2022) 26 *Journal of Industrial Information Integration* 100257

Suchismita Pahi and Calli Schroeder, 'Extended Privacy for Extended Reality: XR Technology Has 99 Problems and Privacy Is Several of Them' (28 August 2022)

Susanne Barth, Dan Ionita, and Pieter Hartel, 'Understanding Online Privacy—A Systematic Review of Privacy Visualizations and Privacy by Design Guidelines' (2022) 55 *ACM Computing Surveys* 63:1

T. Mulder & M. Tudorica (2019) Privacy policies, cross-border health data and the GDPR, *Information & Communications Technology Law*, 28:3

Terry Yue Zhuo and others, 'Exploring AI Ethics of ChatGPT: A Diagnostic Analysis' (arXiv, 22 February 2023)

Wolfgang Kerber, 'Governance of IoT Data: Why the EU Data Act Will Not Fulfill Its Objectives' (2023) 72 *GRUR International* 120

Y. Wang et al., "A survey on metaverse: Fundamentals security and privacy", arXiv preprint, 2022

Yogesh K. Dwivedi and others, 'Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Emerging Challenges, Opportunities, and Agenda for Research, Practice and Policy' (2021) 57 *International Journal of Information Management* 101994

Others

ENISA, *Cybersecurity Market Analysis Framework V2.0*, March 2023; ENISA, *Identifying Emerging Cyber Security Threats And Challenges for 2030*, March 2023.

European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, "Horizon 2020 Programme Guidance: How to complete your ethics self-assessment", Version 6.1, 23 May 2023.

European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), (2017), *Necessity Toolkit*, Brussels, 11 April 2017.